

IHI Project ID - SYNTHIA

Synthetic Data Generation Framework for Integrated Validation

WP8 – Ethical, legal and societal issues

D8.1 DPIA results

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Term
AD	Alzheimer's Disease
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
AIA	Artificial Intelligence Act
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BC	Breast Cancer
CFREU	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
CNIL	<i>Commission Nationale de l'Informatique et des Libertés</i>
DLBCL	Diffuse Large B-Cell Lymphoma
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPA	Data Protection Authorities
DPF	EU-U.S. Data Privacy Framework
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
DSA	Data Sharing Agreement
EC	European Commission
ECHR	European Convention on Human Rights
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EEA	European Economic Area
EFPIA	European Federation of Pharmaceutical Industries and Associations
EHR	Electronic Health Records
ELSI	Ethical, Legal, and Societal Impact Issues
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FINDATA	Finnish Social and Health Data Permit Authority
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
ICFs	Informed Consent Forms
ICO	The UK's Information Commissioner's Office
iHD	The European Institute for Innovation through Health Data
LC	Lung Cancer
MM	Multiple Myeloma
MS	Member State
PET	Privacy-enhancing technologies
RWD	Real World Data
SCC	Standard Contractual Clauses
SD	Synthetic Data
SDG	Synthetic Data Generation
T2DM	Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus
VM	Virtual Machine

Executive Summary

This deliverable contains the results of the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) carried out for the SYNTHIA project by the University of Vienna (leader of WP8- Ethical, legal and Societal issues) in fulfilment of Task 8.1 (under the Grant Agreement) and in accordance with the requirements of GDPR Article 35. GDPR mandates that a DPIA must be conducted where, inter alia, the processing of personal data is envisaged at a large scale or involves special categories of personal data (which may include health data) or involves the use of novel technologies (which may include AI) — and where such processing of personal data may lead to a high risk to data subjects rights.

The DPIA, therefore, aims to evaluate the risk-impacts of the envisaged processing operations within the SYNTHIA project, which involves personal data. The objective of the DPIA is to demonstrate compliance with the GDPR's data protection principles and ensure that the data subjects' rights are not negatively impacted. This assessment thereby encompasses all the processing operations during the SYNTHIA project, including the development and validation of SYNTHIA (Synthetic Data Generation) tools and Synthetic Datasets, through the disease-specific Use Cases.

Relatedly, this document contains a brief summary of the nature, source, scope, and purpose of personal data processing, data management, and data flows in the project and offers a legal assessment of the adequacy of the organizational, technical, and security measures employed (or planned) across the full range of project activities involving personal data. As guidance intended to inform and improve the data protection compliance of/the SYNTHIA consortium, the DPIA concludes with key findings of the impact assessment, practical recommendations, and suggested next steps. To ensure a more rigorous review of data protection compliance, the results of this DPIA have been sent to and validated by DPOs of SYNTHIA consortium partners. This DPIA does not exclude the SYNTHIA Beneficiaries from having to conduct their own DPIA at the individual level to the extent so required by applicable laws and regulations or internal policies.

Outline and Structure of DPIA

The DPIA incorporates, addresses, and identifies the following topics and/or questions. Part I details the aims, scope, and nature of the project and data processing (including the legal bases for such data processing), and types of personal data to be processed. Moreover, since the conduct of DPIA necessitates a collaborative process involving all the consortium entities providing, sharing, receiving, or otherwise processing personal data, the section will also include information pertaining to the methodology of how information for DPIA was collected, along with details of stakeholder consultation (including information on which stakeholders, for e.g. project partners and/or their Data Protection Officers and/or privacy experts have been consulted/contacted, and a summary of their responses).

Since the SYNTHIA project involves processing substantial volumes of personal data to design, plan, train, and validate both SD and SDG, conducting a DPIA necessitates the collective input and coordinated actions of all relevant stakeholders regarding data management. With over 30 specialized partners from diverse fields collaborating, structured and rigorous deliberation is essential to identify data protection risks from technical, clinical, and other domain-specific perspectives. This collaborative process fosters a unified understanding of risks and mitigation measures while ensuring that all parties clearly comprehend their data protection roles and obligations. Ultimately, it strengthens trust in the project's data protection framework, enhances compliance, and enables the DPIA to accurately represent the project's data protection strategy.

Part I: This section provides an overview of the legal framework and the specific context within the SYNTHIA project regarding the processing of personal data and clearly establishes the rationale and legal grounds for conducting the DPIA.

Part II: This section outlines the security framework implemented across the SYNTHIA consortium to safeguard personal data, in accordance with Article 32 of the GDPR. It is intended to provide a wider snapshot of personal data processing activities in the project. It will include a mapping of data flows that describes who will have access to personal data, and for what purposes; how the data will be collected, stored, and shared. Given the processing of sensitive health data by project partners, robust technical and organizational measures are mandatory to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of data.

The consortium comprises multiple partners employing diverse infrastructures, including cloud-based, on-premises, and federated systems, adapted to their institutional policies and regulatory obligations. While some partners have finalized their technical setups, others are in the process of defining infrastructure and security arrangements. This dynamic situation will be continuously monitored and reflected in subsequent DPIA updates.

This section also includes an overview of partner-specific infrastructures, software solutions, and security practices currently implemented or planned, alongside considerations on data service locations and cross-border transfers (in particular, the transfer of personal data outside of the EU).

Part III: This section deals with the exercise of carrying out risk assessment. In view of the security, organizational, and technical means for data protection in the project, this part describes risk identification, assessment, and mitigation measures (details of the risks that may arise in the context of SYNTHIA, as well as an assessment of the likelihood and severity of the risks along with relevant measures to combat, prevent, minimize or otherwise mitigate such risks), also including information on duration and details of data storage and/or retention. Relatedly, it also includes an assessment of controls protecting data subjects' rights and how those subjects can exercise such rights. In sum, Part III, therefore, evaluates the impact of data processing in the SYTHIA project and identifies and assesses the various risks that may arise, and to the extent they have been mitigated.

Relatedly, since the DPIA is intended to provide a practical rule-guiding assessment of current data protection measures, Part 3 will also include concrete solutions and/or recommendations for the consortium partners to (further) enhance data protection practices. The DPIA section will therefore also include, where applicable, any plans for the implementation of relevant solutions/recommendations. As the concluding section, this part also provides a brief summary of the DPIA results.

Here, it must be noted that some or most of this information about personal data may already exist in the other project documents, such as Grant Agreement (GA), Use Case Study Protocols, Data Management Plan (DMP), and/or Data Sharing Agreement(s) (DSA), and therefore, such information, as much as possible, is cross-referenced, for the ease of comprehension and avoidance of repetition.

Part I: Introduction - DPIA context and purposes

What is a DPIA, and why is it needed for SYNTHIA?

Under the SYNTHIA Grant Agreement, task 8.1 deals with the provision of ethical and legal frameworks and guidance to assist partners with compliance issues, mainly pertaining to data protection. As the SYNTHIA project deals with processing personal data (including RWD and clinical trial data), it is essential to establish legal frameworks, create legal documents, and develop guidance that helps with setting up and initiating data sharing within the consortium in an ethically safe and legally compliant manner. In view of this, in fulfilment of task 8.1, led by the University of Vienna (UNIVIE), this document contains a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA), the finalized results of which are due in month 12, as per the Grant Agreement. **The DPIA is meant to assist the consortium partners in understanding and achieving their respective ethical, legal, and privacy compliance requirements and in submitting the relevant information required for Ethics Committee applications.**

This first version of the DPIA is to be read closely within the guiding framework of the Grant Agreement (GA), the Data Management Plan (DMP) as well as other project documents that detail (or otherwise deal) with personal data processing, in particular the Study Protocol(s) comprising the various use cases, and the Data Sharing Agreement (DSA) that will be set up at the Consortium level. As per the EU's main data protection legislation governing personal data, General Data Protection Regulation (Regulation (EU) 2016/679) ('GDPR'), the data controllers must continuously assess the risks created by their processing activities. Therefore, if needed, the DPIA will be updated during the timelines of the SYNTHIA project in view of any material changes in the nature, scope, or context of personal data processing, and such changes may be reflected in the subsequent versions of the DMP and DPIA.

Thus, in essence, the DPIA refers to an evaluation process that is required under Article 35 GDPR. A DPIA essentially describes the processing of personal data, assesses its necessity and proportionality, and explains the risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons that arise from the processing of personal data while also assessing the origin, nature, and severity of such risks.¹ Equally important, as the name implies, as it is an impact assessment, it also evaluates such risks and explains the mechanisms that are executed (or planned) to avert, mitigate, or otherwise control or minimize those risks.² In accordance with the GDPR's risk-based approach, conducting a DPIA is not mandatory for all processing operations. Rather, a DPIA is only required where the processing involves 1) personal data, and where such processing is likely to 2) result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons (Article 35; recital 84 GDPR).

DPIAs are an important tool for legal compliance. The conduct of DPIA is to be understood within the context of the overall obligation of data controllers to adopt measures to ensure and demonstrate data protection compliance. Such data protection obligation of the data controller(s) is set out in Article 24(1) GDPR, which requires data controllers to implement (and if required, review and update) appropriate technical, organizational, and security measures to ensure data protection in consideration of the nature, scope, context and purpose of processing and the risks such processing may pose to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.

However, DPIAs are important, not only for legal compliance purposes (as required under GDPR), but they also serve other useful organizational and functional purposes. For instance, the execution of DPIAs aids in accountability. The DPIA helps to structure the already existing data protection legal obligations upon data controllers, such as compliance with GDPR principles, and documentation requirements (like keeping records of data processing, and description of security measures, etc.)

¹ Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) – EDPS.

² ARTICLE 29 DATA PROTECTION WORKING PARTY - Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679.

under a structured compliance scheme guided by the risk-based focus of the GDPR.³ Seen this way, DPIAs help demonstrate the appropriateness of measures that have been taken by the data controllers to ensure data protection.⁴ For the data subjects and the wider public, the DPIA may aid in transparency and help provide confidence, assurance, and trust in the data protection practices of the controller's processing operations.⁵

Methodology: How is the DPIA conducted?

Since WP8 is the ELSI work package (dealing with legal, ethical requirements, and societal impact), conducting a DPIA (in line with GDPR requirements) is designated as a contractual requirement for WP8 under the SYNTHIA Grant Agreement (under task 8.1, and the results of which are to be reported in deliverable D8.1).

The DPIA is primarily a legal exercise that aims to provide a critical assessment of the adequacy of the data protection risks that arise out of the envisioned data processing activities by the data controller(s). Therefore, the DPIA may be seen as elucidating the legal requirements for data protection and seeing the extent to which such requirements may be met by the data controllers in view of their data processing activities. While the focus of DPIA is primarily on the rights of data subjects as contained within the EU Laws (most particularly, the GDPR), the scope of the impact assessment may also be extended to include broader social or ethical impacts of such personal data processing. Such an assessment requires an evaluation of the purposes, scope, context, and means of processing of personal data against the human and fundamental rights of data subjects.

Therefore, this DPIA process involves the collection of information that is of critical legal importance in understanding the entire data trajectory within the SYNTHIA project. To gather such information and detailed insights on data processing practices, risks, and mitigation measures, a designated questionnaire was prepared by WP8. All consortium partners were actively consulted via this questionnaire, which contained questions seeking specific information for all the SYNTHIA consortium partners and shedding light on their individual or collective involvement in all the activities that relate to personal data. Such information is of a technical and organizational nature and provides the necessary context for WP8 to conduct the Impact Assessment. Such a questionnaire was prepared by WP8 and circulated to the relevant consortium parties (from November 2024 to February 2025). The questionnaire is attached as **Annex 1** to this document. A list of consortium partners who participated in this questionnaire is also provided as **Annex 2** to this document.

The information obtained from the responses to this questionnaire is further confirmed and clarified by UNIVIE's receipt of information via email exchanges, and attendance at regular work package and coordination meetings within the SYNTHIA project.

The consultation aimed to ensure all relevant stakeholders could provide input regarding the management of personal data, security practices, and risk identification specific to their data processing activities. This initial consultation process involved direct engagement with partner organizations' data protection officers and/or privacy experts, and/or internal research group, IT security specialists, and data governance teams to ensure accuracy and completeness. Further consultation will take place as infrastructure details become clearer, particularly for partners who (in their responses) indicated that final decisions regarding software solutions and security measures remain pending. Where applicable, consortium partners committed to seeking views internally from their data protection officers (DPOs) and/or privacy experts, IT security experts, and legal teams to align with GDPR requirements and best practices.

The consultation revealed no immediate requirement to directly seek individuals' views at the patient

³ Data Protection Impact Assessment: A tool for accountability and the unclarified concept of 'high risk' in the General Data Protection Regulation --- Katerina Demetzou.

⁴ Privacy Impact Assessment Methodology.

⁵ Data Protection Impact Assessment Case Study for a Research Project Using Artificial Intelligence on Patient Data.

level since most partners do not directly interact with data subjects; instead, data subject consultations are managed at the data provider level. However, partners are committed to maintaining transparency and will consider further stakeholder engagement as the project evolves, particularly if processing activities or risk profiles change.

Given the technical complexity and sensitive nature of certain data sets, ongoing consultation with IT security experts and technical staff within each partner organization will continue throughout the project's lifecycle. Stakeholders such as data providers and data users will be regularly engaged through structured feedback loops, especially at the project's critical milestones, to address emerging concerns and to reinforce trust in SYNTHIA's handling of personal data. Collaboration will involve continuous interaction with the Data Protection Officer and/or privacy experts, IT department, project management team, and legal and compliance advisors, ensuring thorough oversight and effective response to emerging risks or compliance challenges throughout SYNTHIA's duration.

Moreover, the risk-assessment analysis part also benefits from a list of authoritative legal resources and official guidelines, most notably, including Article 29 Data Protection Working Party's guidelines on (conducting) DPIA; ('*Commission nationale de l'informatique et des libertés*' The French National Commission on Informatics and Liberty) ('CNIL') Privacy Impact Assessment Guidelines; European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS)'s principles for conducting DPIA; iHD's Assessment Checklist for DPIA; DPIA templates from the UK's Information Commissioner's Officer as well as other scholarly legal literature and legal practice manuals.

The results obtained from this questionnaire were used to conduct a Data Protection Impact Assessment. The report containing such an assessment (the earlier version of this document) was sent for review to SYNTHIA partners and their DPOs. As a matter of good compliance practice, the results of DPIA were also shared with the Data Protection Officers (DPOs) and/or privacy experts of the relevant SYNTHIA consortium entities for their comment and validation. This document is the final version of the DPIA results, that have been finalised in view of feedback and review from all such parties.

As discussed earlier, if required, further on in the project, the DPIA may be revised if there is a material change in the nature, purpose, scope, and context of personal data processing, which might warrant such a fresh impact assessment. This is a project-wide DPIA and is designed to support each partner in their compliance requirements. This DPIA can be used by consortium partners to conduct their own (entity-level) DPIAs where applicable. The applicable data protection legislation and regulations

The processing of personal data in the project is governed by the European Data Protection laws, most particularly, the GDPR, the member states' (where consortium partners are located) national implementing legislations, as well as any other applicable national/regional laws on data protection. Among the most important regulatory requirements for (personal) data processing relate to adherence to the data protection principles including due regard to lawfulness, fairness, and transparency (of processing operations), purpose limitation, data minimization, storage limitations, and (the necessity to have in place) appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure data protection (please refer to the Data Management Plan and the Data Sharing agreement that will be set up at the Consortium level for further elaboration of these legal principles). Moreover, data entities providing, sharing, receiving, or otherwise *processing* personal data in the project must also ensure that they have a valid legal basis/es to do so (for the purposes of the SYNTHIA project) and that they remain in compliance with all the EU laws as well as any relevant national/local data protection laws and/or regulatory approval processes (for instance, Ethics Committees). The details concerning personal data management and data flows are also reflected in the Data Sharing Agreement, which complements this DPIA and the DMP, together forming the core framework for data processing in the SYNTHIA project. For avoidance of doubt, it must be noted that GDPR defines processing very broadly to include a wide range of dealings with personal data. As per article 4(2) GDPR:

“processing” means any operation or set of operations which is performed on personal data

*or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction*⁶.

What does a DPIA entail? The minimum legal content of a DPIA

The DPIA is to be conducted before the commencement of the processing, since it is meant to implement the GDPR's data protection by design and default principle (article 25 GDPR), with the view that DPIA can inform the decision-making concerning the processing. This is because DPIA allows data controllers to assess the technical feasibility of the system in line with legal requirements.⁷ DPIAs may facilitate the data controllers in adopting a structured and well-considered way of approaching the risk-mitigation frameworks in line with the GDPR principle of 'data protection by design', where it is needed the most, i.e., for high-risk processing.⁸

The DPIA thus consists of a highly inclusive and comprehensive procedure that encourages the data controllers to consciously consider the data protection principles and obligations right at the very beginning of the processing operations. The DPIA thus has an ex-ante, proactive nature and thus helps prevent harm to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.⁹ While the GDPR does not formally provide a template of what a DPIA shall contain, it nonetheless provides the minimum content of what a DPIA shall entail. As per Article 35(7)¹⁰, with respect to personal data processing, a DPIA shall consist of the following essential elements: 1) a systematic description of the envisioned processing operations, including its purpose; 2) an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of such processing with respect to the purposes of the processing; 3) assessment of the risks that may arise from such processing, and correspondingly; and 4) the steps envisaged to address, mitigate, minimize or otherwise prevent such risks along with details of any safeguards, security measures and other mechanisms that are (or will be) put in place to ensure data protection in view of the rights and interests of those are likely (actually or potentially) affected by such data processing. While the risks are mainly understood to be related to the rights and freedoms of data subjects, primarily the rights to data protection and privacy, consideration may also be had to other fundamental rights, construed broadly.¹¹

The DPIA may be carried out by any internal personnel or an external entity (such as sub-contractors with the necessary expertise); however, ultimately, the data controller(s) remain responsible for ensuring that the DPIA is carried out (Article 35(2)).

Roles of consortium partners in data processing: (Data) Controllers and Processors

As per articles 24-29 GDPR, the entities involved in or dealing with personal data processing will be designated as either data processors or (Joint) Data Controllers. Any personal data processing, therefore, requires the data protection roles and obligations as processors or controllers to be identified, outlined, and clearly set forth for information and compliance purposes for the relevant consortium entities. WP8 is tasked with addressing such legal needs of the project and the corresponding regulatory issues and serves as an ethical and legal helpdesk for all the consortium partners in connection with their data protection responsibilities that lie within the scope of the SYNTHIA project. The roles of the partners and corresponding responsibilities will also be further

⁶ Article 4(2) GDPR

⁷ Data Protection Impact Assessment Case Study for a Research Project Using Artificial Intelligence on Patient Data.

⁸ Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) – EDPS.

⁹ Data Protection Impact Assessment: A tool for accountability and the unclarified concept of 'high risk' in the General Data Protection Regulation --- Katerina Demetzou.

¹⁰ All references in the citations refer to GDPR, unless stated otherwise.

¹¹ ARTICLE 29 DATA PROTECTION WORKING PARTY - Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679.

detailed in the Data Sharing Agreement that will be set-up at Consortium level.

UNIVIE, as leader of WP8, is indeed, together with other Beneficiaries, already working on creating a Data Sharing Agreement (DSA), which will provide a contractual and legal framework for data sharing in the project, and will identify the legal bases, legal roles, and obligations of various consortium partners. Signing this (DSA) will be a legal requirement in compliance with GDPR and a prerequisite for consortium-wide data sharing.

As the DSA is still in draft form at the time this DPIA is being conducted, the following serves as a preliminary legal guidance: data providers in SYNTHIA (i.e. entities that provide, make available, or otherwise contribute, directly or indirectly (including third parties), any personal data) may *prima facie* be considered Data Controllers for the purposes of the GDPR. Similarly, entities in SYNTHIA that use such data (i.e. consortium partners expected to process this personal data) may, *prima facie*, be considered Data Processors under the GDPR. However, please note that this position is subject to change as the project evolves, particularly as the DSA is negotiated, reviewed, and ultimately signed, which (DSA) will more accurately reflect the final and definitive allocation of roles and responsibilities.

While the specifics of such role assignment and allocation are being determined in the preparation of the DSA, it may be noted that entities that are Data Controllers that jointly determine the means and purposes of data processing may be collectively designated as Joint Controllers. Likewise, it is also possible that different consortium partners may have different data protection roles, owing to their respective data processing dealings involving (the same or varying) personal data. For instance, for the provision of one cohort of personal data to the SYNTHIA project, an entity may be a Data Controller (either independently or jointly, depending on the factual determination of such role in the project), while at the same time, it may also be a Data Processor in respect to processing another cohort of personal data that is contributed by other SYNTHIA consortium partner(s). Once again, please note that this position is stated here as initial guidance and is subject to change during the drafting, negotiation, and review of the DSA.

Please note that such a determination of roles is a matter of factual evaluation and, therefore, needs to be assessed on a per-processing activity basis, in view of the partner's tasks and functions. More information on these data protection roles and corresponding obligations will be provided by WP8 leader UNIVIE and in the Data Sharing Agreement to be set-up in due course. As per clause 3.7 of Annex 2 CA, each Beneficiary is solely responsible for complying with applicable Data Protection Legislation, including evaluating its role as Controller, Joint Controller or Processor in relation to a Work Package and/or a Work Package task under the Project such Beneficiary participates.

When should a DPIA be conducted? The legal requirement of when a DPIA is due

The DPIA is a legal obligation upon Data Controllers that becomes applicable in certain situations where there is likely to be high risk. The GDPR does not provide an exhaustive list of situations when the processing of personal data may likely result in high risks to the rights and freedoms of natural persons.¹² Nonetheless, as a guide, it lists specific instances¹³ where such may be the case (and therefore, necessitating a DPIA). As per Article 29 Data Protection Working Party's Guidelines¹⁴ (WP29), some of these instances, (of most relevance to the SYNTHIA project) include situations where:

1) Processing involves a high volume of special categories of personal data (sensitive data) referred to in Article 9(1) GDPR (art.35(3)(b)). Such personal data includes genetic data and data concerning

¹² Article 35(3) GDPR.

¹³ See for instance, Article 9(1), article 35(1), 35(3) and recitals 89 and 91 GDPR.

¹⁴ Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk" for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679.

health¹⁵.

2) Data processed on a large scale: this is to be determined in view of the number of data subjects (whose data is processed), the volume and/or range of data items being processed, the duration of data processing activity, and/or the geographical extent of the processing activity.

3) The data processing involves innovative use of or application of new technology: the use of a new technology defined in accordance with the state of technological knowledge (Article 35(1), recitals 89 and 91 GDPR) may trigger the need to conduct a DPIA. This is due to the fact that the use of novel technologies may create new and unprecedented risks since the personal and societal consequences of the use of new technology may be unknown.

As per WP29, the more criteria are met by the processing, the more likely it is that the processing of personal data involves a high risk to the data subjects' rights and freedoms, and therefore, necessitating the carrying out of a DPIA, irrespective of the measures which the controller(s) plan to implement.

We may see that all three (above-mentioned) conditions are satisfied in the context of the SYNTHIA project. In a plain language summary, it may be stated that the SYNTHIA project aims to develop Synthetic Data (SD) models for healthcare applications. The project is expected to generate both tools for SD generation as well as SD datasets comprising various data modalities (including genomics and imaging). With such an aim, the project will use sensitive special categories of data (as defined in Article 9(1) GDPR) to develop, train, and validate the generated SD tools and outputs. Such personal data may comprise both retrospective patient data as well as (in some cases) prospectively collected data (from clinical studies) for various Use Cases. Each use case covers a specific disease. Thus, SD models and data are envisioned to be generated using real patient data (which may also include RWD and data collected from clinical trials). Therefore, it can be said that the conditions specified by Article 29 WP (concerning the processing of personal data on a large scale as well as processing special categories of personal data both apply here.

Likewise, it may also be noted that SYNTHIA aims to harness the power of AI to generate SD. The use of AI would most likely qualify as the use of new technologies, where the full risks of AI usage may yet be unknown, or the full impact of their usage may necessitate precaution. SD using AI would be artificially generated data that captures and mimics the patterns (including statistical distribution and dependencies) of original patient data. While the use of AI-generated SD may be beneficial in the field of healthcare applications, the AI (technology) specific risks this may generate include the potential risk of identification of patient data (used to create such SD) from the SD datasets and the risks of perpetuation of bias in the original datasets (upon which such SD tools and datasets) were trained/based. All this means that the need to conduct a DPIA remains paramount, especially given the AI's highly sophisticated generation methods of SD. Thus, a DPIA will not only help the SYNTHIA consortium comply with the GDPR requirements but also identify issues of legal, technical, and (biomedical) industry-specific quality criteria, standards, and regulatory controls that pertain to the development and use of AI technologies in the field of healthcare.

Therefore, it may be concluded that the three specific instances of high-risk processing (mentioned above) are satisfied, and a DPIA shall be carried out for the SYNTHIA project.

SYNTHIA partners are also advised that where applicable, they shall (as data controllers) consult and/or obtain prior approvals from the relevant supervisory authorities (whenever required by the Member state laws) where the processing may relate to the performance of a task carried out in the public interest, including processing in relation to public health (art. 36(5) and that they conduct their own DPIA if and to the extent required.

¹⁵ art.9(1) GDPR

Data Processing: What (personal) data will be processed in the SYNTHIA project, and for what purposes?

SYNTHIA envisions using special categories of data (as defined by Article 9 GDPR), in particular health data. The personal data may include both retrospectively collected health data as well as prospectively collected health data. The retrospective data may consist of various categories, including Real World Data (RWD), data from Electronic Health Records (EHR), data from Observation Studies, and data from clinical trials (made available by private EFPIA members) – to be finalised in the due course of the project timeline. The access to and provision of such personal data will be used for the development of SDG, and such personal data may be appropriately converted, pre-processed, or standardized (including data-quality control measures) to render them suitable for use in the SYNTHIA project.

The data to be used for the SYNTHIA project will be provided by various partners working on the use cases. These use cases are disease-specific and comprise solid tumours [(Lung Cancer (LC), and Breast Cancer (BC)]; haematological malignancies [(Multiple Myeloma (MM), and Diffuse Large B-cell Lymphoma (DLBCL)]; and non-oncological ones: [a neurodegenerative disease (Alzheimer's disease (AD), and a chronic metabolic disease (type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM)]. Such division has been made to ensure that SDG can be developed and validated for applications to various disease profiles.

Currently, the use cases (including the research scope, research questions, and the guidance protocols) are still under development, and once the arrangements are finalised concerning the specific protocols and criteria of use, each data provider will contribute data as per the requirements of the use case. Moreover, it will also be agreed on how and which data is to be processed by each data user in the SYNTHIA project. More updated information and details on this can be found in the Clinical Study Protocol (prepared by WP3) as well as the updated versions of the Data Management Plan (prepared by WP1) and in the Data Sharing Agreement once established. Moreover, in addition to such data for use cases, it is also envisioned that WP9 will introduce an additional use case to assess the use of SD in Health Technology Assessment (and for any related regulatory purposes). The data for this will be provided (or generated from) one of the disease-specific use cases. It will be seen whether such data would qualify as personal data, and if so, all applicable personal data protection obligations will have to be complied with.

On the following pages, find a brief tabularized summary of the main data sources and data providers, along with types and formats of data. This information is drawn from the collected responses to the DPIA questionnaires, the latest available Data Management Plan (prepared by IISLAFE, version 1, February 2025), the Study Initiation Packages for various use cases (deliverables D7.05 to D7.10), and the corresponding Study Protocol Templates. While every effort has been made to include only the most up-to-date materials (reflecting the latest versions of the Study Initiation Packages and Study Protocol Templates available as of 11 August 2025), it must be cautioned that the information provided below is only tentative and is subject to change in the light of developments and changes in the project. For any related queries and information about the data sources, please contact WP3, which deals with use case analysis and requirements.

Case Study 1: Use of SD to improve lung cancer detection, monitor the disease/effect of medical treatment, and outcomes prediction

Data provider	Data Type	Data Format	Data users	Additional information on data sets from the respective Study Initiation package and the Study Protocol Template
IISLAFE	CT scan, Data Warehouse (DW) clinical data., clinical notes	DICOM, OMOP-CDM, JPG + Text	UNIBO GEHC IISLAFE	<p>Biomedical Imaging Platform: A longitudinal de-identified dataset of 700 lung cancer patients collected between 2014 and 2024 through an electronic Case Report Form. It includes comprehensive clinical variables (e.g., diagnostics, lab results, treatments, procedures) and associated CT scans. The data, which is currently structured in an OMOP-like CDM, is intended for reuse through federated learning in the IISLAFE's CPD (Data Processing Center).</p> <p>Big Data Platform: The Big Data Platform of IIS La Fe integrates clinical, epidemiological, and biological information at the individual level from the population assigned to the Valencia La Fe Health Department, as well as from patients referred to the hospital due to its role as a regional and national reference center. This dataset spans at least from 2012 onwards. The DW contains structured, pseudonymised data from various care areas, services, and units within the health department, along with more than 30 million unstructured records. All data sources are linked via a common identifier. Currently, the platform hosts clinical records from corporate information systems, which are stored locally and harmonised to the OMOP CDM. This dual structure allows for flexible data management and reuse, supporting both native system formats and standardised analytical workflows. These systems continuously feed the platform with pseudonymised data, updated on a daily basis. In collaboration with the Medical Oncology Department,</p>

			and as part of a jointly executed study, a curated cohort of approximately 700 patients diagnosed with lung cancer has been developed and clinically validated. This cohort is available within the broader data ecosystem managed by the platform and intended for reuse, when necessary, through federated analysis modalities.
UNIBO (IRCCS-AOSP.S.Orsola – AE)	CT, PET, clinical, and histopathological images	DICOM, pending to map to OMOP-CDM	<p>UNIBO will contribute multiple datasets, including both institutional and public sources:</p> <p>Collection S. Orsola Data Warehouse for reuse: Approximately 2,000 records collected during routine clinical care, including CT and PET images data, histopathology slides (to be digitalized) and genomic data with a 50-mutation gen panel.</p> <p>Public Dataset – NLST: Up to 50,000 cases from the National Lung Screening Trial (NCT00047385), a randomized study evaluating the efficacy of low-dose CT screening versus chest X-rays. The dataset includes imaging and associated clinical data.</p> <p>Public Dataset Supplementary: 25,000 additional cases from the same NLST cohort, including 26,254 low-dose CT scans and digitized histopathology slides from 451 participants.</p>
HUS	derived from EHR	OMOP-CDM, Tabular	The dataset from HUS is a longitudinal, de-identified collection derived from electronic health records (EHR) of lung cancer patients treated at the largest specialized healthcare provider in Finland. It is a large and comprehensive dataset with data included from 2014 onwards, covering approximately 9,100 records available for secondary use. The dataset includes tabular

			data in OMOP CDM v5.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.
CHA	CT scan, basic clinical data	DICOM, pending to map to OMOP-CDM	<p>Data from own collections as well as clinical studies – for reuse in federated modality. For example, Charité might provide access to a curated dataset developed within the CHAIMELEON project (H2020 GA n° 951272) or provide a similar dataset comprising approximately 250 pseudo-anonymised patient records. The dataset will include longitudinal EHR data with structured clinical variables and imaging (CT and PET), curated for secondary research reuse and compliant with data protection requirements.</p> <p>Each dataset offers unique characteristics in terms of size, modality, and level of curation, contributing to the diversity and robustness of data sources for synthetic data generation and validation in the lung cancer use case.</p>
ICH	Multimodality	DICOM, Tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM.	<p>ICH will provide access to data repositories for various subtypes of lung cancer, hosted in its research data infrastructure (ICH Data Lake). The dataset includes structured clinical and potentially imaging data, suitable for research purposes.</p>

Case Study 2: Use of SD data for tissue and lesion models, and treatment response prediction models in breast cancer

Data provider	Data Type	Data Format	Data users	Additional information on data sets from the respective Study Initiation package and the Study Protocol Template
IISLAFE	MRI, DW clinical data, clinical notes	<p>EUCAIM is not structured in OMOP CDM format</p> <p>DICOM, OMOP-CDM,</p> <p>JPG + Text</p>	<p>GEHC</p> <p>IISLAFE</p>	<p>EUCAIM: IISLAFE's own collections in EUCAIM (anonymized, OMOP, clearance for reuse): Data set Collection IISLAFE (collections in EUCAIM - EUCAIM is co-funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement N° 1011100633). It includes clinical data from 1,700 patients diagnosed with breast cancer between 2014 and 2024, with a follow-up period of up to 12 months. The dataset is not structured in OMOP CDM format. It comprises comprehensive clinical variables suitable for secondary use, including diagnostic information, laboratory results, procedures, and drug treatments. Additionally, the dataset includes 200 associated breast MR scans corresponding to cases within the cohort, as well as mammography (MMG) data for all patients.</p> <p>Big Data Platform: The Big Data Platform of IIS La Fe integrates clinical, epidemiological, and biological information at the individual level from the population assigned to the Valencia La Fe Health Department, as well as from patients referred to the hospital due to its role as a regional and national reference center. This dataset spans at least from 2012 onwards. The DW contains structured, pseudonymised data from various care areas, services, and units within the health department, along with more than 30 million unstructured records. All data sources are linked via a common identifier. Currently, the platform hosts clinical records from corporate information systems, which are stored locally and harmonised to the OMOP CDM. This dual</p>

			structure allows for flexible data management and reuse, supporting both native system formats and standardised analytical workflows. These systems continuously feed the platform with pseudonymised data, updated on a daily basis.
HUS	Derived from the EHR of patients	OMOP-CDM, Tabular	Data set Collection HUS BIG DATA PLATFORM: The Breast Cancer dataset is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at HUS (Helsinki University Hospital), the largest provider of specialized healthcare in Finland.). It is a large and comprehensive dataset with data included from 2014 onwards, covering approximately 29,300 records available for secondary use. At least 1,000 BC patients with metastatic disease treated with CDK inhibitors have been identified for UCB. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM v5.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.
VHIO/VHIR	Standard biomarkers, digital pathology, digital mammography, genetic tests	DICOM, OMOP-CDM	Data source is a combination of human-curated BC registry data (REDCap from 2016 onwards, OMOP for oncology) + electronic health record (EHR) data from VHIO (physician notes, laboratory data, medical reports). The BC dataset is an early-stage BC cohort with longitudinal and de-identified data that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at Vall de Hebron Hospital, the largest provider of tertiary care in Catalonia. It is a large and comprehensive dataset in REDCap (institutional registry from real-world) with data included from 2016 onwards, manually curated to OMOP covering 2,280 patients available for secondary use, with complete information on outcome (BC relapse, new primaries, death). In terms of imaging data, 1,703 cases have

				<p>mammography, 1,142 magnetic resonance imaging (792 with both imaging modalities). Also, VHIR/VHIO has performed a detailed analysis of the data dictionaries for our BD registry and EUCAIM project (see below), to harmonize de UCA early BC data collection.</p>
CHA	Basic clinical data, mammograms, MRI, histopathology, and treatment data	DICOM, pending to map to OMOP-CDM		<p>Data from own collections as well as clinical studies – for reuse in federated modality. The CHA Breast Cancer dataset is a longitudinal and pseudo-anonymized dataset that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at CHA. It is a comprehensive dataset with tabular and imaging data included from 2015 onwards, covering approximately 2,000 records available for secondary use. The dataset includes basic clinical and imaging data (mammograms, MRI), manually curated with laboratory results, histopathology, molecular information, as well as procedures/drug treatments.</p>
LUMC	Mammograms, genetic test results, risk, and treatment data	DICOM, tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM		<p>The LUMC (Leiden University Medical Center) is one of the data centers in a national network called the HEreditary Breast and Ovarian cancer study Netherlands study (Hebon). Hebon is a collaboration between all clinical genetic departments in the Netherlands (from all eight university medical hospitals and the Netherlands Cancer Institute), providing specialised care for families with breast and ovarian cancer. This network focuses on familial breast cancer and prospectively collects clinical information on women undergoing DNA-testing for this indication. This includes DNA-test results, questionnaire data on breast cancer risk factors, treatment data (surgeries, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, etc.), and pathology data.</p> <p>Hebon regularly performs linkages to the Netherlands Cancer Registry and the Dutch</p>

			<p>Pathology Registry (PALGA), to keep track of new cancer incidences in the cohort. A few years ago, the network started to collect mammography images from women under surveillance and at increased risk to develop breast cancer. A DNA-test result is presently available for >40,000 women, approximately 10,000 of whom carry a known pathogenic variant in a known breast cancer susceptibility gene. Subsets of the cohort participate in international consortia studies such as BCAC, ENIGMA and CIMBA.</p> <p>The Hebon dataset is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the questionnaires and national registries data of participants. It is a large and comprehensive dataset with data included from 1997 onwards, covering approximately 30,000 records available for secondary use. The database is highly structured and was subject to a previous FAIRification project. The dataset includes tabular data in CSV-format structured with questionnaires data about risk factors and lifestyle, registry data on incidence and pathology, and genetic test results, diagnoses and treatments, and imaging data in DICOM-format structured with mammograms data. Access to data contained in the HEBON database requires a formal data application request to the network, which will be evaluated by a data access committee.</p>
ICH	Multimodality	DICOM, tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM	<p>Humanitas Research Hospital data warehouse (ICH Data Lake – for research) The Breast Cancer EUSOMA) is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset collected from different collection in the EHR of patients treated at ICH (Humanitas Research Hospital). It is a dataset with data included from 2018 onwards, covering approximately 500 records available for secondary use. With data on early-stage Breast</p>

				<p>Cancer) The dataset includes tabular data in structured format with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions for different breast cancer subtypes. Data is collected at diagnose, with follow-up data (longitudinal also available).</p>
Pfizer	Electronic data collection form, patient-reported outcomes, longitudinal clinical trial data.	OMOP-CDM		<p>The PERFORM study retrospective since 2020 and prospective ongoing until 2028 aims to enrol 1,900 subjects across Germany and Austria to gain insights on effectiveness, tolerability, patient-reported outcomes. And the PALOMAGE study is another real-world cohort study conducted in France in women aged ≥ 70 years with HR+ HER2 negative metastatic BC.</p>

Case Study 3: Use of SD for external control arm in clinical trials and to improve outcomes prediction through integration of imaginal and genomic data in Multiple Myeloma

Data provider	Data Type	Data Format	Data users	Additional information on data sets from the respective Study Initiation package and the Study Protocol Template
IISLAFE	DW clinical data, clinical notes	OMOP-CDM, tabular	UNIBO IISLAFE UPM	<p>The Big Data Platform of IIS La Fe integrates clinical, epidemiological, and biological information at the individual level from the population assigned to the Valencia La Fe Health Department, as well as from patients referred to the hospital due to its role as a regional and national reference center. This dataset spans at least from 2012 onwards. The DW contains structured, pseudonymised data from various care areas, services, and units within the health department, along with more than 30 million unstructured records. All data sources are linked via a common identifier.</p> <p>Currently, the platform hosts clinical records from corporate information systems, which are stored locally and harmonised to the OMOP CDM. This dual structure allows for flexible data management and reuse, supporting both native system formats and standardised analytical workflows. These systems continuously feed the platform with pseudonymised data, updated on a daily basis. In collaboration with the Medical Oncology Department, and as part of a jointly executed study, a curated cohort of approximately 300 patients diagnosed with MM has been developed and clinically validated. This cohort is available within the broader data ecosystem managed by the platform and intended for reuse, when necessary, through federated analysis modalities. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.</p>

UNIBO (IRCCS-A – AE)	CT, PET, CNV, ctDNA, clinical variables, genomics, transcriptomics	DICOM, Tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM, sequencing data (fastq), processed data (BAM/CRAM)	The Multiple Myeloma dataset is a de-identified dataset that is derived from the HR of patients treated at the Institute of Hematology “Seragnoli” - IRCCS Sant’ Orsola, Bologna (Italy). It is a large and comprehensive dataset with data included from 1997 to 2020, covering approximately 350 records available for secondary use. The dataset includes tabular uniformed data including laboratory results, FISH genetic alterations data, drug treatments, therapy responses and survival outcomes.
ICH	Multimodality	DICOM, tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM	Humanitas Research Hospital data warehouse (ICH Data Lake – for research). ICH is collecting a unique repository for SYNTHIA since 2004 and head CT is part of the data collection. The data set is available for secondary use, after ICH internal ethical approval. The dataset includes diagnose, with follow-up data as part of standard clinical practice at EHR (longitudinal also available) and includes type of treatment, response to treatment, clinical outcomes and Radiology / histopathology data. MRI data is collected as part of standard care practice for response to treatment.
HUS	Tabular, possibly flow cytometry data	OMOP-CDM, tabular	HUS’ Big Daa Platform (OMOP, for reuse in federated modality). The Multiple Myeloma dataset is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at HUS (Helsinki University Hospital), the largest provider of specialized healthcare in Finland.). It is a comprehensive dataset with data included from 2014 onwards, covering approximately 1,300 records available for secondary use. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM v.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.

CHA	Clinical data, including treatment, imaging, genomics, transcriptomics, and proteomics	DICOM, pending to map to OMOP-CDM		<p>Data from own collections as well as clinical studies – for reuse in federated modality.</p> <p>Data set Collection CHARITE. The MM dataset is a longitudinal and pseudo-anonymized dataset that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at CHA. It is a comprehensive dataset with tabular and imaging data included from 2015 onwards, covering approximately 500 records available for secondary use. The dataset includes routine clinical and imaging data manually curated with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.</p>
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Case Study 4: Use of SD for treatment response prediction using Minimal Residual Disease in Diffuse Large B-Cell non-Hodgkin Lymphoma (DLBCL)

Data provider	Data Type	Data Format	Data users	Additional information on data sets from the respective Study Initiation package and the Study Protocol Template
IISLAFE	DW clinical data,, notes	OMOP-CDM, tabular	CERTH BSC UNIBO CHUV	<p>The Big Data Platform of IIS La Fe integrates clinical, epidemiological, and biological information at the individual level from the population assigned to the Valencia La Fe Health Department, as well as from patients referred to the hospital due to its role as a regional and national reference center. This dataset spans at least from 2012 onwards covering approximately 300 records available for secondary use (UC 4.1).</p> <p>The DW contains structured, pseudonymised data from various care areas, services, and units within the health department, along with more than 30 million unstructured records. All data sources are linked via a common identifier. Currently, the platform hosts clinical records from corporate information systems, which are stored locally and harmonised to the OMOP CDM. This dual structure allows for flexible data management and reuse, supporting both native system formats and standardised analytical workflows. These systems continuously feed the platform with pseudonymised data, updated on a daily basis. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM v5.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.</p>
HUS		OMOP-CDM, tabular		<p>HUS Academic (OMOP, for reuse in federated modality)</p> <p>The DLBCL dataset is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at HUS (Helsinki University Hospital), the largest provider of specialized healthcare in Finland). It is a comprehensive dataset with data included from 2014 onwards, covering records for approximately</p>

			1400 patients available for secondary use. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM v5.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.
UNIBO (IRCCS- A - AE)	Imaging	The data will be only Imaging (PET and CT), no sequencing.	<p>UNIBO (S. Orsola Research Hospital data warehouse)</p> <p>The data hosted in the PACS (Picture Archiving and Communication System) system of the S.Orsola University Research Hospital affiliated to UNIBO are all in the DICOM format and are CT and PET images of the DLBCL. For all the data we have a diagnosis provided by the nuclear doctor (the nuclear medicine MD). The diagnosis can be: positive, negative and doubtful (doubtful case). The data will be shared mainly with UNIBO and subsequently shared in a federated way with selected partners. The number of patients we hope to reach by the end of the project is about 2000.</p>
ICH	Multimodality	DICOM, tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM	<p>Humanitas Research Hospital data warehouse (ICH Data Lake – for research)</p> <p>ICH is collecting a unique repository for SYNTHIA, where data cover approximately 500 records with data available for secondary use. The Data includes diagnoses, with follow-up data as part of standard clinical practice at EHR (longitudinal also available) and includes type of treatment, response to treatment, clinical outcomes and Radiology / histopathology. From 2024, PET CT is also part of the collection.</p>
CHA	Clinical data, imaging, genomics/ transcriptomics/ proteomics	Pending to map to OMOP-CDM, tabular	<p>Data set Collection CHARITE</p> <p>The DLBCL dataset is a longitudinal and pseudo-anonymized dataset accumulated from medical data collected from patient care as well as clinical studies – for reuse in federated modality that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at CHA. It is a comprehensive dataset with tabular and imaging data, covering approximately 500 records available for secondary use from 2015 onwards. The dataset includes</p>

				routine clinical and imaging data manually curated with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.
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Case Study 5: Use of SD for predictive models for diagnosis based on imaging and fluid biomarkers, and the evaluation of the potential for synthetic control arms in Alzheimer's Disease (AD)

Data provider	Data Type	Data Format	Data users	Additional information on data sets from the respective Study Initiation package and the Study Protocol Template
IISLAFE	DW clinical data, clinical notes, MRI, PET, CSF biomarkers, neuropsychological scores	OMOP-CDM, DICOM, JPEG, Tabular	Fraunhofer SCAI Fraunhofer MEVIS IRCCS-S UNIBO	IISLaFe (Hospital Uni-versitari i Politècnic La Fe) will provide a dataset from the cognitive impairment unit (from 2017 to 2024). The AD dataset is a cross-sectional and de-identified dataset that is derived from the patients treated at IISLAFE. The dataset includes clinical data from 676 patients diagnosed with AD between 2017-onwards. It includes tabular data with demographic variables, laboratory results (CSF biomarkers, genetics), neuropsychological tests, MRI, PET, and drug treatments. The data will be OMOPed before sharing with SYNTHIA.
IRCCS-S, an affiliated entity of UNIBO	MRI, clinical data, cognition, epigenetics	DICOM, Tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM		<p>both retrospective and prospective data will be included in the study, and these data will be OMOPED before sharing with SYNTHIA.</p> <p>Retrospective data: they will include clinical, neuropsychological, imaging, liquor and blood analyses collected in the framework of clinical routine (up to X past years) or in the framework of the following studies:</p> <p>Prospective data: they will include clinical, neuropsychological, imaging, liquor and blood analyses collected in the framework of clinical practice or in the framework of the following studies, already approved by the local IRCC-S Ethical Committee, that will be performed in the period 2025-2027:</p> <p>PNRR-MCNT2-2023-12377357 - Integrating Sleep-wake oscillatory activities and Liquid biopsy as innovative biomarkers for multimodal diagnosis in preclinical and prodromal Alzheimer's disease.</p>

				PE0000006 MNESYS – “A multiscale integrated approach to the study of the nervous system in health and disease” – Spoke 6 WP2 Task 2 – Studio del contributo genetico ed epigenetico alla neurodegenerazione nell’ambito del Partenariato Esteso MNESYS
LUMC	Questionnaires, physical examination, MRI, multimodal, Cognition, clinical data, blood, CSF, MRI, RNASeq, snRNASeq, Imaging, genetic, cognitive, biomarkers	DICOM, Tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM		<p>Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC) aims at providing two datasets of a rare AD type: LUMC CAA and LUMC CAA Long to be used by the LUMC partners within SYNTHIA. Both datasets contain collected data of Cerebral Amyloid Angiopathy (CAA) patients from the LUMC CAA cohort study (LUMC CAA), which is a cohort study collected at LUMC in hereditary Dutch-type CAA patients, sporadic CAA patients and controls, designed to investigate the specific pathology of this rare neurodegenerative and cerebrovascular condition that distinguishes it from Alzheimer’s disease. LUMC CAA is a small dataset with data included from 2018, covering data of 9 Dutch-type CAA cases and 9 controls available for secondary use.</p> <p>The dataset includes clinical, RNASeq and snRNASeq data in tabular format as CSV-format. LUMC CAA is open and can be requested. The LUMC CAA Long dataset is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the collected data of hereditary and sporadic CAA patients as well as age-matched controls from the LUMC CAA cohort study. It is a small dataset with data included from 2015 onwards, covering approximately 150 records available for secondary use.</p> <p>The LUMC CAA Long dataset will currently not be publicly available due to the sensitive nature of these data of ultra-rare hereditary CAA patients but will be accessible for the LUMC partner in SYNTHIA. The dataset includes longitudinal follow-up cognitive, clinical, blood and CSF data in tabular format as CSV-format and MRI data in DICOM-format. LUMC will also make use of publicly available</p>

				databases such as ADNI, ROSMAP and the Rotterdam Study.
HUS	Derived from the EHR of patients	OMOP-CDM, tabular		<p>The AD dataset is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at HUS (Helsinki University Hospital), the largest provider of specialized healthcare in Finland.).</p> <p>It is a comprehensive dataset with data included from 2014 onwards, covering approximately 20.800 records available for secondary use. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM v5.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions</p>
GV	Clinical data, cognitive data, imaging, biomarkers	DICOM, tabular, OMOP-CDM		<p>Gates Ventures provided four different multi-center cohort studies and one RCT to partner FH, each designed to assess the clinical, economic, and humanistic impact of AD in community-dwelling patients and their caregivers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GERAS EU: Conducted in France, Germany, and the UK, this 18-month study enrolled 1,530 patients between October 2010 and September 2011. In some centers, an extended follow-up until 36 months was performed. • GERAS II: Conducted in Italy and Spain, this study took place between 2013 and 2014, enrolling 584 patients (198 in Italy, 380 in Spain). • GERAS Japan: Conducted in Japan, this 18-month study ran from 2016 to 2017, enrolling 560 patients. • GERAS US: Conducted in the United States, this 36-month study enrolled 1,5388 patients between 2016 and 2018. <p>Additionally, the A4 study was also obtained for the synthetic control arms task.</p> <p>A4 (solanezumab RCT). The A4 Study database contains longitudinal data from cognitively</p>

				<p>unimpaired participants aged 65-85 with elevated amyloid plaque accumulation, collected across 67 sites. It includes biomarkers, cognitive assessments, and clinical information, and aims to evaluate the impact of solanezumab on slowing cognitive decline in Alzheimer's at pre-symptomatic stages. Fully enrolled in 2017 with 1169 participants, the study tests whether anti-amyloid treatment can delay cognitive decline and related brain injury.</p> <p>In addition, FH has access to cohort studies that are widely used in the scientific community, such as ADNI.</p>
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Case Study 6: Use of SD for digital biomarkers from non-invasive wearables for glycaemic event monitoring and analysis of the impact of diabetes treatment on cardiovascular complications

Data provider	Data Type	Data Format	Data users	Additional information on data sets from the respective Study Initiation package and the Study Protocol Template
IISLAFE	DW clinical data, clinical notes	OMOP-CDM, tabular	BSC Fraunhofer ITMP	<p>IISLAFE provides access to retrospective, longitudinal dataset of 1,110 pseudonymised patients with T2D, overweight or obesity and cardiovascular risk who were seen in the Endocrinology department between 2017 and 2024. The study variables will be obtained from electronic medical records (EMR), which include structured and unstructured data. The data source will be the Big Data AI Biostatistics and Bioinformatics Platform, which contains clinical, epidemiological and biological information at the individual level of its assigned population cohort (300,000 people) and of patients admitted as a reference centre, at least since 2012. In addition to these population cohorts, there is a historical dataset of approximately 1.5 million patients.</p> <p>This information is stored in a Data Warehouse (DW) composed of the aggregation of 22 data marts; organised in 750 million rows, 84 tables and 4,064 columns, which are updated daily, weekly or monthly. This DW contains pseudonymised structured information from different areas, services and health units of the department. In addition, it contains 40 million unstructured records. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM v5.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, pharmacological treatments and drug prescriptions.</p>
HUS	Derived from the EHR of patients.	OMOP-CDM, DICOM, JPEG		Helsinki University Hospital (HUS) holds a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the EHR of patients treated at HUS (Helsinki University Hospital), the largest provider of specialized

				healthcare in Finland). It is a comprehensive dataset with data included from 2014 onwards, covering approximately 48.800 records available for secondary use. The dataset includes tabular data in OMOP CDM v5.4 structured with laboratory results, procedures, drug treatments, and drug prescriptions.
ICH	Multimodality	Tabular, pending to map to OMOP-CDM		Humanitas Research Hospital's data contribution is pending completion of internal review and ethical approval expected in October 2025. Preparations for data structuring and clinical validation are ongoing.
NOVO	Multidomain data from clinical trials and observational studies, including data from CGMs and other wearables (Fitbit, apps)	To be determined		For the Hypo-RESOLVE data, trial data from 26 clinical trials involving 12,247 people living with type 1 diabetes and 65 trials involving 34,007 people living with type 2 diabetes were provided by industry partners. All trials involved people with diabetes who were taking glucose-lowering medication with hypoglycaemia risk, mostly insulin. The raw trial data were standardised, harmonised and pooled in a unique hypo-RESOLVE database by the Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, using the Clinical Data Interchange Consortium (CDISC) Study Data Tabulation Model Implementation Guide (SDTMIG 3.2). In addition, the bespoke domain XH was created for hypoglycaemia event data, obtained from self-recorded episodes in participants' diaries and serious adverse event declaration from clinical trials. The trials did not use CGM. Some episodes were asymptomatic episodes noted on self-monitored blood glucose that met the agreed thresholds for hypoglycaemia, and some were symptomatic episodes. Level 3 (see below) episodes did not require a blood glucose measurement as this was not part of the definition, although it was often recorded. Some level 3 episodes were derived also from serious adverse event reporting. Each hypoglycaemia event was characterised by an event date, a blood glucose measurement (if

			<p>available) and self-treatment status.</p> <p>The Hypo-METRICS study is a prospective observational study involving nine clinical centres across five European countries and is part of the EU IMI2 Hypo-RESOLVE (Hypoglycaemia – REdefining SOLutions for better liVEs) programme [15]. Ethical approval was granted in each of the five countries.</p> <p>Briefly, the study involved the following elements: (1) assessment of daily functioning, captured with the Hypo-METRICS app [13], three times daily for 70 days; (2) continuous measurement of interstitial glucose via a blinded sensor (Abbott FreeStyle 2 Libre; Alameda, CA, USA) (i.e. data unavailable to the participants) modified to collect data every 5 min; (3) baseline collection by research staff of demographic and diabetes-related information; and (4) completion of validated self-reported outcome measures online (via Qualtrics, Provo, UT) at baseline and 10 weeks of follow-up and via the Hypo-METRICS app (daily and weekly). Participants were eligible if they were aged ≥ 18 years and belonged to one of the following three groups: (1) type 1 diabetes with intact awareness of hypoglycaemia (Gold score < 4 [17]); (2) type 1 diabetes with impaired awareness of hypoglycaemia (Gold score ≥ 4 [17]); or (3) type 2 diabetes managed with at least one insulin injection per day. Participants also needed to have had at least one episode of hypoglycaemia (symptomatic or confirmed by glucose measurement) in the past 3 months. Participants were recruited via the study sites and via online and offline advertisement. They provided informed consent.</p>
LUMC	Questionnaires, physical examination, MRI, multimodal		<p>Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC) provides access to the LUMC NEO study dataset. The NEO dataset is a longitudinal and de-identified dataset that is derived from the data collection, EHR and questionnaires data of participants from the Netherlands</p>

		<p>Tabular data in CSV-format, imaging data in DICOM-format structured with MRIs, MRS and ECGs.</p>		<p>Epidemiology of Obesity (NEO) study, an ongoing population-based prospective cohort study collected at the Leiden University Medical Center (LUMC) designed to investigate pathways that lead to disease in obesity. The NEO study is a collaborative initiative involving over 10 clinical departments of the LUMC and is coordinated at the department of Clinical Epidemiology. The LUMC is a line organization in the Netherlands that was formed from a collaboration between the Academic Hospital Leiden and the Faculty of Medicine of Leiden University, providing healthcare in the Leiden area.</p> <p>It is a large and comprehensive dataset with data included from 2008 onwards, covering approximately 6,671 records of people living in the greater area of Leiden in the Netherlands that are available for secondary use. The dataset includes tabular data in CSV-format structured with questionnaires data, physical examination and multimodal data from baseline measurements and laboratory analyses and imaging data in DICOM-format structured with MRIs, MRS and ECGs.</p>
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Part II: Organizational, Technical, and Security Measures for Data Protection in SYNTHIA

The inclusion of this section is essential to demonstrate how data security is ensured across the SYNTHIA consortium. In line with Article 32 of the GDPR, data controllers and processors are required to implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to safeguard personal data. Given that SYNTHIA partners may process sensitive health data, the infrastructure and software used for secure data handling, storage, and processing must meet high standards of confidentiality, integrity, and availability. This section provides an overview of the security infrastructure and software environments used by consortium partners (including central server if and where applicable), helping to assess whether appropriate safeguards are in place to mitigate risks associated with unauthorized access, data loss, or system vulnerabilities. By outlining each partner's approach, this section supports the DPIA's objective of evaluating the risk landscape and ensuring robust data protection practices throughout the project lifecycle.

The SYNTHIA project involves multiple partners, each implementing different infrastructure solutions to ensure secure data processing. The selected infrastructure varies based on institutional policies, data types, and security measures. Below is an overview of the infrastructure solutions reported by partners.

Partner	Infrastructure solutions and architecture
NICE	To be determined based on data access requirements. Updates to be provided in future DPIAs.
HUS	HUS Academic , an SPE running on Azure. ¹⁶ The cloud-based (Azure) infrastructure, air-gapped with several virtual machines, including GPU-equipped VMs, to ensure high security.
UPM	WP5: To be concretized in the package. WP6: Local solutions.
PFIZER	Not determined yet.
CERTH	CERTH is not going to collect data; thus, CERTH is not considered a key data management node as it will mostly develop individual scripts to be used for SDG. However, it should be noted that CERTH's computational infrastructure is certified for ISO 27001 and thus all the necessary steps are applied to ensure data information security. Plans to develop individual scripts, without a specific architectural infrastructure.
DNV	Infrastructure and architecture depend on the data provider and data provided, and will be determined based on data access requirements. DNV is ISO 27001 certified.
EMBL	BioModels for hosting SG-generating models.

¹⁶ <https://www.hus.fi/en/research-and-education/tutkijan-palvelut/hus-academic-secure-operating-environment>.

	BioStudies for SD generated in SYNTHIA.
	EGA for hosting both.
GEHC	If a federated environment is used, GEHC has no control over infrastructure/security. If data is transferred, potential solutions include:
	Research & Analytic Data Store (RADS) - cloud-based secure data storage
	On-premises data storage (e.g., NAS) and processing solutions located in Budapest (Hungary), Munich (Germany), and Buc (France)
VHIO	Infrastructure will be developed internally and implemented on-premises with full GDPR compliance. The infrastructure architecture decision depends on data specifics and is not yet finalized.
IISLAFE	Uses a secure, dedicated infrastructure through IIS La Fe and hospital servers, compliant with necessary regulatory requirements. On-premises high performance computer data processing centre of the IIS La Fe in compliance with the national security scheme.
IISLAFE	IBM Cloud-based platform:
	IBM Watsonx Lakehouse
	IBM Cloud Pak 4 Data Fabric
	PET (Privacy-Enhancing Technologies) for federated learning.
GV	Not processing data directly, but aims for synthetic data discoverability via the EPND Catalogue. ¹⁷ Supports the AD Data Initiative, which operates infrastructure based on national regulatory requirements; specific details depend on the roles of each partner.
FRAUNHOFER	Internal processing with the ADDI Workbench.
LUMC	FAIR Data Points and FAIR Data Stations for local computation.
JANSSEN	Infrastructure and architecture depend on the data provider.

¹⁷ discover.epnd.org/catalogue/studies.

UNIBO	8 dedicated Workstations and privileged access to HPC facilities.
NOVO	Not determined yet.
IRCCS-S	On-premises infrastructure for collection, storage, harmonization, pseudoanonymization, and data processing. Connected to IRCCS-S LAN. Infrastructure architecture includes a secure combination of data storage solutions, servers, and secure communication protocols.
IRCCS-A	On-premises infrastructure for collection, storage, harmonization, pseudoanonymization, and data processing. Connected to the IRCCS-A LAN. Infrastructure architecture includes a secure combination of data storage solutions, servers, and secure communication protocols.
CHA	On-premises infrastructure will be developed to meet project needs and GDPR compliance. Infrastructure architecture is still to be determined.
i-HD	Not applicable.
BMS	Not applicable.
ERASMUS	Not applicable.
ITTM	Provides dedicated servers and virtual machines for secure data processing. Can provide resources from the T4 data centre in Luxembourg, but no plan yet.
CHUV	Will use hospital-trusted research environment. Specific infrastructure details are pending.

The SYNTHIA project involves multiple partners utilizing different cloud-based, on-premises, and federated infrastructures for secure data processing. The selected architecture depends on institutional policies, security requirements, and the type of data processed.

Several partners have indicated that the choice of infrastructure is yet to be determined or clarified.

The SYNTHIA consortium includes a diverse range of institutions—academic centres, hospitals, industry partners, and SMEs—each operating under different internal IT policies, legal frameworks, and readiness levels. As a result, while some partners have already established definitive infrastructure and security frameworks, others are still in the process of determining their final technical setups. These differences stem from several factors, including the timing of data access, the nature of the data to be processed, internal approval workflows, and dependencies on national regulations or ethics approvals. This variance is expected in large, multi-partner research projects involving complex and sensitive data.

From a DPIA standpoint, incomplete infrastructure details pose a limitation on fully assessing technical and organizational safeguards as required under Article 32 GDPR. Accordingly, such cases will be subject to continued follow-up and reviewed in future iterations of the DPIA, once more detailed information becomes available. This ensures the DPIA remains a dynamic and responsive tool that evolves alongside the technical and operational maturity of the project. If there are any material changes in the nature, scope, and extent of data processing in the project, a fresh DPIA will be conducted, and results (of which) and any revisions will be added as updates to this document.

Each partner's infrastructure is selected or designed with specific security, data protection, and compliance requirements in mind, aligning with the GDPR and relevant national regulations. Specific details for several partners remain pending and will be clarified once data specifics are finalized. Each partner remains responsible for keeping compliant with the GDPR requirements and maintaining the appropriate levels of organizational security and technical measures at their respective entities. This responsibility includes conducting their own DPIAs, where applicable.

Software and Third-Party Applications

Several partners indicate that software solutions are yet to be determined or clarified.

The following table outlines the software and third-party applications each SYNTHIA partner intends to use for management and service provision on their infrastructure:

- NICE: Software and applications are yet to be determined based on the types of data received and their sources.
- HUS: Utilizes Linux and Windows virtual machines (VMs), including GPU VMs and Azure cloud services.
- UPM: WP5 specifics remain to be concretized. For WP6, Ubuntu and Windows operating systems with on-premises equipment will be employed.
- PFIZER: Software solutions to be confirmed.
- CERTH: Plans to use the "CDM inspection" script provided by the DARWIN EU initiative and/or other similar quality assurance codes (e.g., the ones provided by the OHDSI community). Other open-source software libraries could also be used (this is to be decided).
- DNV: Software choices are still to be decided.
- EMBL: Will implement Linux, Kubernetes, Ansible, Terraform, and HPC Slurm schedulers.
- GEHC: Will operate Linux (Ubuntu) servers in virtual machines located in on-prem server rooms
- VHIO: No external or third-party software is planned for the initial phase.
- IISLAFE: Will run infrastructure, including Linux-based servers.
- GV: Not applicable as they will not process any data.
- FRAUNHOFER: Will use self-designed software written in Python.
- LUMC: Software solutions will be developed collaboratively within the SYNTHIA project.
- JANSSEN: Software choices depend on the data provider's specifications.
- UNIBO: Plans to utilize Linux and Windows systems and open-access software, developed in-house (Python and R).
- NOVO: Software solutions yet to be defined.

- IRCCS-S: Servers operate on Debian 12 Bookworm Linux distribution.
- IRCCS-A: Plans to utilize Linux and Windows systems.
- CHA: Software solutions still to be defined. This will depend on actual implementation of the services by the IT department and requirements from the different work packages.
- BMS: Not applicable.
- ERASMUS: Not applicable.
- ITTM: Employs managed services provided by its vendor.
- CHUV: Information pending collection from internal IT resources. FDP

Routine Updates of Service Software

Routine updates of software are essential to maintain security, performance, and compliance standards within SYNTHIA. Each partner has committed to ensuring regular updates, reflecting good practice and adherence to established IT management protocols. The frequency and nature of updates vary, with some partners employing automated systems while others manage updates manually, following internal guidelines or vendor recommendations. Below is an overview of the routine service software update practices among SYNTHIA partners:

- NICE: Regularly updates both security and service software following standard practices.
- HUS: Follows Azure guidelines for routine software updates.
- UPM: Confirms routine updates.
- PFIZER: Update frequency and practices to be confirmed.
- CERTH: Employs automated updates for Linux (Ubuntu LTS), with manual updates for other OS/software as needed. This software will be used for the building and testing of relevant scripts.
- DNV: Regular software updates confirmed.
- EMBL: Routinely updates service software.
- GEHC: Applies urgent security patches promptly and schedules regular software updates quarterly.
- VHIO: Has established change management policies ensuring regular software updates.
- IISLAFE: Confirms routine software updates in line with their IT protocols.
- GV: Not applicable due to no data processing activities.
- FRAUNHOFER: The IT department manages regular software service updates.
- LUMC: Software updates managed by the LUMC IT department, with internal responsibility for updates if the software is project-specific.
- JANSSEN: Update policies to be drafted by MBC.
- UNIBO: Confirms routine software updates.
- NOVO: Routinely updates service software following established internal guidelines.

- IRCCS-S: Software updates are performed automatically by the Debian Linux system.
- CHA: Software updates will be conducted according to internal Charité guidelines.
- BMS: Not applicable.
- ERASMUS: Not applicable
- ITTM: Confirms routine software updates.
- CHUV: Confirms routine software updates.

Service Locations and Data Transfers Outside the European Economic Area (EEA)

Understanding the geographic location of services is crucial for ensuring compliance with GDPR requirements related to international data transfers. SYNTHIA partners have provided details regarding where their services are hosted and whether these are within or outside the EU. Currently, no transfers of personal data out of the EU are envisioned. However, in case of transfer of personal data outside of the EU, or partners hosting services outside the EU, they must adhere to additional compliance obligations under GDPR. These can include the use of appropriate safeguards such as adequacy decisions,¹⁸ by the European Commission (Article 45), Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs) approved by the Commission (Article 46), or, where applicable, Binding Corporate Rules (Article 47). Relying on appropriate mechanisms, such as adequacy decisions by the European Commission, where available, may be essential for maintaining the lawfulness, fairness, and transparency of data processing across borders.¹⁹ In case of data transfer to the U.S., the EU-U.S. Data Privacy Framework (DPF) will be applicable. DPF is developed by the U.S. Department of Commerce and the European Commission to provide U.S. organizations with reliable mechanisms for personal data transfers to the U.S. from the EU while ensuring data protection that is consistent with EU, UK, and Swiss law.

Below is an overview of the service locations for each partner:

- NICE: Services run from the United Kingdom, outside the EEA.
- HUS: Services hosted in Azure Europe North, within the EEA.
- UPM: All services are hosted locally within the EEA.
- UNIBO: All services are hosted locally within the EEA.
- PFIZER: Location details to be confirmed.
- DNV: Services and data processing will be run within the EEA.
- EMBL: Services hosted in the UK, outside the EEA.
- GEHC: Services hosted partly outside the EEA (US-based servers) and partly within the EEA (Hungary, Germany, or France-based servers).

GEHC reports that pseudonymized personal data will be processed by EU-based personnel, with a backup copy stored in RADS, a cloud-based solution hosted on AWS servers in the

¹⁸ "An adequacy decision is a formal decision made by the EU which recognises that another country, territory, sector or international organisation provides an equivalent level of protection for personal data as the EU does." (Source: [Adequacy | ICO](#))

¹⁹ For UK please check: [Documents - European Commission](#), The decision is valid until 27 December 2025. This will allow time for the legislative process to conclude in the UK. Once concluded, the Commission will assess the new legal framework and decide on its adequacy. In the meantime, the UK data protection rules that were found adequate in 2021 remain in place and continue to apply to data transferred from the EU. Partners are reminded to consult their legal teams and remain updated on the legislative developments in this regard.

United States. As AWS is certified under the EU-U.S. Data Privacy Framework (DPF)²⁰ This transfer can rely on the adequacy decision under Article 45 GDPR, provided the processing falls within the scope of that certification.

GEHC should ensure that this setup is documented and that DPF requirements are fully met. If needed, additional safeguards such as Standard Contractual Clauses (SCCs) and technical measures may be applied. The necessity of storing data outside the EEA should also be periodically reviewed by the relevant SYNTHIA partners in line with GDPR's data minimization and storage limitation principles.

- VHIO: All services hosted within the EEA (Spain).
- IISLAFE: Services hosted at the data processing centre of La Fe Hospital and IIS La Fe, Valencia, within the EEA. We can operate in a hybrid local-cloud environment. This setup integrates the on-premises HPC IIS La Fe Data Center and the infrastructure of the hospital's Data Center with IBM Cloud services hosted in Spain, enabling coordinated data processing and secure communication between both environments.
- GV: Not applicable due to no data processing activities.
- FRAUNHOFER: Services hosted internally and on the AD Workbench (some study data being processed by Fraunhofer is hosted in the US but processed within Azure data centres in the EU).

Fraunhofer has reported that their services are hosted both internally and on the AD Data Initiative's AD Workbench, without specifying the geographic locations of these servers. The AD Workbench is a secure, cloud-based data-sharing and analytics environment developed by the Alzheimer's Disease Data Initiative. According to their privacy statement, personal data collected through their services may be stored and processed in various countries, including Ireland, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, among others.²¹

Given that the AD Workbench operates across multiple jurisdictions, Fraunhofer needs to determine and document the specific data storage locations utilized for its projects. This information is crucial to ensure compliance with data protection regulations, particularly concerning international data transfers under the GDPR. If personal data is stored or processed outside the EEA, appropriate safeguards—such as SCC or reliance on adequacy decisions—must be implemented and/or documented to demonstrate compliance.

Therefore, Fraunhofer should engage with the AD Workbench administrators to clarify the exact locations of data storage and processing relevant to their use case. This will enable a comprehensive assessment of data transfer implications and ensure that all necessary legal and technical measures are in place to protect personal data.

- LUMC: Utilizes both LUMC VMs²² and external cloud services within the EEA.
- JANSSEN: Location dependent on data providers; details to be clarified per case.
- NOVO: Services are primarily hosted from within the EEA.

²⁰ "The EU-U.S. DPF, UK Extension to the EU-U.S. DPF, and Swiss-U.S. DPF were respectively developed by the U.S. Department of Commerce and the European Commission, UK Government, and Swiss Federal Administration to provide U.S. organizations with reliable mechanisms for personal data transfers to the United States from the European Union, United Kingdom, and Switzerland while ensuring data protection that is consistent with EU, UK, and Swiss law." <https://www.dataprivacyframework.gov/>; <https://www.dataprivacyframework.gov/list>; <https://aws.amazon.com/de/privacy/>

²¹ The ADDI privacy statement does not provide a specific list of these other locations. Instead, it indicates that data may be processed in any country where ADDI or its service providers operate. The statement also mentions that personal data may be transferred to countries outside the European Economic Area (EEA), the UK, and Switzerland-including countries that may not have been determined by the European Commission to have adequate data protection. ADDI further claims that when they do so, they use legal mechanisms, including contracts, to help ensure rights and protections. (<https://www.alzheimersdata.org/privacy>)

²² "Virtual Machine" is a software-based simulation of a physical computer.

- IRCCS-S: Services hosted internally at IRCCS-ISNB within the EEA.
- IRCCS-A: Services hosted internally at IRCCS-ISNB within the EEA.
- CHA: Services will be hosted internally at the Charité within the EEA.
- BMS: Not applicable.
- ERASMUS: Not applicable.
- ITTM: All services hosted within the EEA.
- CHUV: Services hosted internally by the IT Department in Switzerland,²³ outside the EEA.

²³ In its report of 15 January 2024, the EU determined that Switzerland has an adequate level of data protection based on the GDPR as well. Therefore, transfers of personal data to Switzerland are lawful in accordance with Article 45 of the GDPR. Furthermore, CHUV shall comply with all local data protection laws and the requirements of Swiss legislation and ethics authorities. (Source: <https://www.edoeb.admin.ch/dam/edoeb/en/dokumente/datenschutz/20240115%20EC%20Adequacy%20decision%20EN.pdf.download.pdf/20240115%20EC%20Adequacy%20decision%20EN.pdf>)

Part III: Risk Assessment, results, and recommendations

Fundamental Principles

The processing activities undertaken within SYNTHIA must respect the fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects as outlined in the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the GDPR. These rights include the right to respect private and family life (Article 7 CFR), the right to the protection of personal data (Article 8 CFR), and the right to non-discrimination (Article 21 CFR).

The processing of health data, which constitutes special category data under the GDPR, requires particular attention to ensure that fundamental rights are not disproportionately impacted. The DPIA has evaluated how these rights might be affected by SYNTHIA's data processing activities.

The risk assessment conducted within this DPIA incorporates consideration of these fundamental rights when evaluating potential impacts and determining appropriate safeguards. Where tensions exist between scientific research purposes and individual rights, SYNTHIA implements appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure a balanced approach that respects both societal benefits and individual protections.

To this end, in this section the legal bases for the processing of personal data have been identified; the implementation of data subjects' rights within the SYNTHIA system has been explored; the risks that the processing activities in SYNTHIA pose to the fundamental rights and freedoms of data subjects have been identified, appropriate mitigating measures have been detailed, and the level of risk—including residual risk—has been assessed.

a) What are the Legal Bases for the Processing of the Data?

The processing of health data is lawful when it is based on a legal basis established by the controller under the EU and/or national laws. These legal bases, for instance, may include reliance on Articles 6 and 9 of the GDPR, and, where applicable, under conditions set out in national law.

According to the Grant Agreement (GA), SYNTHIA does not include tasks aiming to collect new (prospective) data. In case prospective data will be collected during the Project, Consortium members might rely on the legal basis established under Articles 6 and 9 of the GDPR and, if applicable, under conditions specified in national legislation. Articles 6(1)(a) and 9(2)(a) of the GDPR permit the processing of personal data, including special categories of data, on the basis of data subjects' consent. In this case, Consortium members must ensure that consent is given freely, is specific, informed, and unambiguous, and complies with other relevant requirements.²⁴ Consortium members, collecting prospective data on the legal basis of consent, assume responsibility for drafting and executing consent forms required to obtain consent from data subjects with the support of UNIVIE if required. Other possible legal bases may include the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or the exercise of official authority (Article 6(1)(e)), and legitimate interests (Article 6(1)(f)), in conjunction with Article 9(2)(j) for scientific research purposes.

²⁴ EDPB, Guidelines 05/2020 on consent under Regulation 2016/679, Version 1.1, Adopted on 4 May 2020.

SYNTHIA is designed to process retrospective data for secondary use. Retrospective data means that the data was not originally collected with the purpose of being used in the SYNTHIA Project. With respect to most retrospective data collected before the start and/or outside the scope of the SYNTHIA Project, Articles 5(1)(b) and 89(1) of the GDPR establish a presumption that the processing of retrospective data, for scientific research purposes, is not considered incompatible with the initial purpose for which the data was initially collected. As SYNTHIA is a scientific research project aiming at improving methods of generating synthetic data and advancing medical research, Consortium members may rely on scientific research purposes as a basis for processing the data. Thus, they may base their processing on Article 6(1)(f), processing necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interest pursued by the controllers involved in the Project, in conjunction with Article 9(2)(j), which establishes that the processing of special categories of personal data is not prohibited, where the processing is necessary for achieving the purposes of scientific research based on EU or EU member state law, as is the case in SYNTHIA.

Alternatively, some of the consortium members may rely on Article 6(1)(e) in conjunction with Article 9(2)(g) or 9(2)(i) of the GDPR. Article 6(1)(e) allows for processing in the public interest, given that the processing of personal data in the SYNTHIA Project is necessary to advance the goals of SYNTHIA as a project carried out in the public interest, namely advancement of public health, as an ultimate goal the use cases aim to improve diagnoses and treatment of relevant diseases. To invoke the public interest of the processing, SYNTHIA Consortium members may rely on the respective EU member state research legislation, applicable to them, in accordance with Article 6(3)(b) of the GDPR.

Article 9 specifically applies to special categories of data, such as health data. Article 9(2)(g) allows for the processing of health data under certain conditions when necessary for reasons of substantial public interest. Article 9(2)(i) permits processing when necessary for public interest reasons in the area of public health. Article 9(2)(j) allows processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, and scientific research purposes, in accordance with Article 89(1) of the GDPR, which provides specific safeguards. In all three cases, processing must be based on Union or Member State law.

While a discussion of possibly relevant legal bases is provided above, ultimately, it remains the legal responsibility of each consortium member to ensure that they have established adequate legal bases/es for their share of any data processing activity within SYNTHIA.

b) Data Sharing Arrangements and the assessment of Roles and Responsibilities under the GDPR

At this stage of the Project, no data transfer from data providers to data users (partners involved in WPs related to SDG) is planned. Therefore, all data users who responded to the DPIA questionnaires indicated that they do not plan to process personal data during the project, as the data will be processed locally via a federated learning platform. However, if it is considered necessary to implement the Project, data providers in SYNTHIA will allow data users to process their personal data on the basis of agreements, including data sharing agreements such as, for example, Joint Controllership Agreements and/or Data Processing Agreements (or a combination thereof), negotiated and signed by the relevant Consortium members with the assistance of UNIVIE and other Beneficiaries involved.

The decision on the appropriate type of agreement must consider data protection roles, which depend on which Consortium partners are involved in determining the purposes and means of personal data processing. While the application of federated learning may reduce the need to transfer data between Consortium partners—and may limit data access, thereby reducing risks to data subjects' rights—it does not automatically mean that data users who do not directly access the data are not data controllers under Article 4(7) of the GDPR.

A key feature of a data controller is the determination of the purposes and means of data processing. In a Consortium setting, it is likely that partners jointly determine these aspects, thereby becoming joint controllers under Article 26(1) GDPR.

As a survey of the EU jurisprudence on data protection reveals, joint decision-making

“can take the form of a common decision taken by two or more entities or result from converging decisions by two or more entities, where the decisions complement each other and are necessary for the processing to take place in such a manner that they have a tangible impact on the determination of the purposes and means of the processing. An important criterion is that the processing would not be possible without both parties’ participation in the sense that the processing by each party is inseparable, i.e., inextricably linked.”²⁵

In a research Consortium where partners have different or overlapping roles—such as data providers, data users (e.g., data analysts, AI specialists), etc.—it is essential to analyse each partner’s role (e.g., auxiliary or advisory vs. core contributions) and their involvement in decision-making regarding the purposes and means of processing personal data.²⁶

c) Implementation of the rights of data subjects

The rights of data subjects include the right to be informed of the processing, the right of access, to data portability, to rectification, restriction, objection, and erasure.

Table: Data Subjects’ Rights according to the GDPR

The right to be informed	<p>When personal data is collected directly from the data subject, the data subject must be provided with the following information:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The identity and contact details of the controller or its representative. • The contact details of the DPO, where applicable. • The purposes for processing. • The legitimate interests pursued by the controller or a third party under Article 6(1)(f). • The recipients of the personal data. • Information about envisaged data transfer outside the EU, if applicable. • Data storage periods. • Rights of the data subject • Existence of automatic decision-making if applicable (Article 13).
The right of access	Data subjects have the right to request access to their personal data (Article 15).
The right to rectification	Data subjects have the right to request the rectification of incorrect or incomplete personal data (Article 16).
The right to erasure	Data subjects have the right to request the deletion of their personal data in certain cases (Article 17).

²⁵ European Data Protection Board: Guidelines 07/2020 on the concepts of controller and processor in the GDPR (2.0). 2021.

²⁶ See Van Veen, Evert-Ben, Martin Boeckhout, Irene Schlünder, Jan Willem Boiten, and Vasco Dias. ‘Joint Controllers in Large Research Consortia: A Funnel Model to Distinguish Controllers in the Sense of the GDPR from Other Partners in the Consortium’. Open Research Europe 2 (9 February 2024): 80. <https://doi.org/10.12688/openreseurope.14825.2>.

The right to restrict processing	Data subjects have the right to obtain restriction of processing in certain contexts (Article 18).
The right to data portability	Data subjects have the right to receive their personal data in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format, and have the right to transmit that data to another controller without hindrance (Article 20).
The right to object to processing.	Data subjects have the right, on grounds relating to his or her particular situation, at any time to process personal data concerning him or her which is based on point (e) or (f) of Article 6(1) (public task and legitimate interests), including profiling based on those provisions. The controller shall no longer process the personal data unless the controller demonstrates compelling legitimate grounds for the processing which override the interests, rights, and freedoms of the data subject or for the establishment, exercise, or defence of legal claims. (Article 21(1)).
The right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing	Data subjects have the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her (Article 22), for instance, the decision on automated establishment of a probability value based on personal data relating to a person and concerning that person's ability to repay a loan in the future.
The right to withdraw consent at any time	Data subjects have the right to withdraw consent at any time; thereafter, all processing of personal data will stop. However, the withdrawal of consent shall not affect the lawfulness of processing based on consent before its withdrawal (Article 7).
The right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority	Data subjects have the right to lodge a complaint with their respective supervisory authority (Article 77).

The rights of data subjects, details on their implementation, and exceptions from corresponding obligations of the data controllers are specified in Chapter 3 (Articles 12-23) and Article 11 of the GDPR. In accordance with Article 11(1), "If the purposes for which a controller processes personal data do not or do no longer require the identification of a data subject by the controller, the controller shall not be obliged to maintain, acquire or process additional information in order to identify the data subject for the sole purpose of complying with this Regulation." As further specified in Article 11(2), "Where, in cases referred to in paragraph 1 of this Article, the controller is able to demonstrate that it is not in a position to identify the data subject...Articles 15 to 20 shall not apply...". In the context of SYNTHIA, this provision means that in the situation of secondary processing, partners are not obliged to identify data subjects to facilitate the implementation of their rights, specified in Chapter 3. As data users in SYNTHIA will process pseudonymized data, therefore, they may consider referencing this Article, along with any applicable national legislation, to support their decision not to engage in direct communication with data subjects.

However, data providers who have a direct relationship with data subjects—such as those collecting data initially—must engage with them through Information Leaflets and Informed Consent Forms (ICFs). These documents must clearly reflect which parties are involved in the processing and for what purposes, in line with the GDPR’s transparency and consent requirements (Articles 12, 13 GDPR).

Additionally, if data users process personal data, they may invoke the exception to the obligation to provide information to data subjects under Article 14(5)(b) of the GDPR. This exception applies to processing for scientific research purposes when providing such information is impossible or would require a disproportionate effort.

d) Retention periods

Regarding data retention, in accordance with Article 5(2)(c) GDPR, all personal data processed within the SYNTHIA project will be retained no longer than is necessary for the purposes for which the personal data are processed. The personal data may be stored for longer periods insofar as the personal data will be processed solely for archiving purposes in the public interest or scientific research purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) subject to the implementation of the appropriate technical and organisational measures required by the GDPR in order to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject. The longer retention periods should be agreed upon between the Beneficiaries.

Each consortium member will establish and document specific retention periods for the data they process, based on the nature of the data, the requirements of the research, and applicable laws and regulations, including those related to clinical trials and observational studies. Once the defined retention period expires, personal data will either be securely deleted or effectively anonymized.

e) Risk assessment

Risk assessment is based on GDPR, in particular Article 24(1), 35, and Recitals 77, 90 GDPR, Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) of the Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (WP29),²⁷ ICO’s DPIA recommendations and template,²⁸ CNIL toolkit,²⁹ Guide of the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD),³⁰ Expert commentary of iHD and guidance from technical and legal experts from UNIVIE and the SYNTHIA consortium.

In this section, first, the potential privacy risks related to the project will be identified and categorized based on their nature and potential impact on the rights of the data subject. Each risk is then assessed for the likelihood and severity of the impact on data subjects’ rights, and mitigation strategies and measures (controls) are developed accordingly. Finally, the level of residual risk, meaning the level of risk remaining after implementing mitigating measures, is assessed in terms of its acceptability.³¹

In identifying and assessing the risks, it was taken into account whether data processing in SYNTHIA could contribute to:

- inability to exercise rights (including but not limited to privacy rights);
- inability to access services or opportunities;
- loss of control over the use of personal data;
- discrimination;
- identity theft or fraud;

²⁷ Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, WP 248 rev.01.

²⁸ <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/uk-gdpr-guidance-and-resources/accountability-and-governance/guide-to-accountability-and-governance/data-protection-impact-assessments/>,

²⁹ CNIL, ‘Privacy Impact Assessment (PIA) Methodology’ (2018) <<https://www.cnil.fr/sites/default/files/atoms/files/cnil-pia-1-en-methodology.pdf>> accessed 17 April 2023.

³⁰ IEPD, Risk Management and Impact Assessment on the Processing of Personal Data, 2021, <https://www.aepd.es/guides/guidelines-conducting-data-protection-impact-assessment-regulatory-development.pdf>.

³¹ IEPD, Risk Management and Impact Assessment on the Processing of Personal Data, 2021, p. 34.

- financial loss;
- reputational damage;
- physical harm;
- loss of confidentiality;
- re-identification of pseudonymised data;
- emotional /psychological distress; or
- any other significant economic or social disadvantage.

Likelihood (Probability of occurrence)	
Level	Description
Remote	It seems difficult for the selected risk sources to materialize the threat by exploiting the properties of supporting assets (e.g., theft of paper documents stored in a room protected by a badge reader).
Possible	It seems possible for the selected risk sources to materialize the threat by exploiting the properties of supporting assets (e.g., theft of paper documents stored in offices that cannot be accessed without first checking in at the reception).
Probable	It seems easy for the selected risk sources to materialize the threat by exploiting the properties of supporting assets (e.g., theft of paper documents stored in the public lobby).

Severity (effects from the perspective of the affected data subjects)	
Minimal	Data subjects may encounter inconveniences, which they will be able to overcome despite a few difficulties.
Significant	Data subjects may encounter significant consequences, which they should be able to overcome, albeit with real and serious difficulties.
Severe	Data subjects may encounter significant, or even irreversible, consequences, which they may not overcome.

Likelihood \ Impact	Minimal	Significant	Severe
Probable	Low	High	High
Possible	Low	Medium	High
Remote	Low	Low	Medium

Level of Residual risk	Definition
Acceptable	The level of recalculated risk after mitigation measures are implemented has been reduced to a threshold that is in line with the GDPR.
Non-acceptable	The level of recalculated risk after mitigation measures are implemented has not been reduced to a threshold that is in line with the GDPR and requires the implementation of additional controls, modification of processing activities, or consultation with the supervisory authority.

SYNTHIA Risk Assessment

Risk Assessment				
Description of Risk	Likelihood	Impact	Overall level of risk (based on likelihood and impact)	Residual Risk Level
Risk 1: Illegitimate access to data, unwanted modification of data, data disappearance, or loss	Remote	Severe	Medium	Acceptable
Risk 2: AI risks including algorithmic bias and discrimination	Remote	Severe	Medium	Acceptable
Risk 3: Patient withdrawing consent	Remote	Severe	Medium	Acceptable
Risk 4: Non-transparent data processing	Remote	Severe	Medium	Acceptable
Risk 5: re-identification of data subjects	Remote	Severe	Medium	Acceptable

Risk 1. Personal data breaches: illegitimate access, undesired modification, and disappearance of data

What are the main risk sources and threats that could lead to this risk?

These risks may arise due to human error, intentional malfeasance, or cyberattacks. In the context of SYNTHIA, these risks may arise at three levels:

- At the level of data providers,
- During the synthetic data generation (SDG) process,
- When the SYNTHIA platform, designed to facilitate long-term user access to extensively validated data, is implemented.

The latter case will not be addressed in this iteration of the DPIA but will be considered at a later stage when more information about the platform's features and infrastructure becomes available.

At the Data Provider Level:

SYNTHIA includes clinical sites such as hospitals (including those affiliated with universities) and health and medical centres as data providers.

At the SDG Level:

SYNTHIA researchers working on SDG must have access to health data to generate synthetic data. This raises concerns regarding unauthorized access, potential modification, or the disappearance of data.

What could be the main impact on the data subjects?

Data processing may impact not only data subjects but also society as a whole.³² Therefore, risk assessment should consider the broader societal implications of data processing within the Project. For SYNTHIA, this is particularly relevant, as the Project aims to contribute to the public good by developing Synthetic Data Generation (SDG) tools and a platform for privacy-preserving data use in healthcare.

Illegitimate access, undesired modification, and disappearance of data mean that the data is being processed by an unauthorized person or in a way that the data subject has not consented, causing infringements to privacy, data protection, and integrity. This results in data controllers' loss of control over the data.

If these risks materialize, they could lead to the reidentification of data subjects and the exposure of their health status or cause other negative consequences for their right to privacy. Furthermore, these threats might affect not only data subjects' rights but could also undermine societal trust in the Project and its outcomes, negatively impacting public opinion on the usefulness and security of the generated SD. These effects will be evident in WP7, which focuses on SD evaluation, quality assurance, and clinical validation. In particular, T7.1 will explore privacy evaluation methods and their applicability to SDG methods and study the effects of formal privacy guarantees on the SD quality. In collaboration with WP8 led by UNIVIE (T8.2), a standardized privacy risk reporting system will be established.

How do you estimate the risk severity?

This risk might have a severe impact on data subject rights, as it involves special category data.

How do you estimate the likelihood of the risk?

Remote. The likelihood of personal data breaches resulting from human error, intentional malfeasance, or cyberattacks appears remote without consortium-level mitigation measures, though existing risks are substantially mitigated through individual partner compliance with national and European data protection legislation. While partners maintain baseline protections through regulatory adherence, consortium-level mitigating measures should provide safeguards aimed to ensure that data processing for the purposes of the Project will not cause personal data breaches.

What mitigating measures will address this risk?

All SYNTHIA data providers are reported to have security measures in place to safeguard the data in accordance with Article 32 GDPR. Hospitals and medical centres ensure that their personnel are properly trained and competent in data collection and handling. Additionally, they must comply with data security standards. To this end, these data providers are required to assess whether a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) under Article 35 is necessary, and, if so, to conduct it to ensure that all necessary safeguards are in place.

One of the security measures adopted by data providers is data pseudonymization. If pseudonymized data is shared, partners will be obliged to adhere to the terms and conditions outlined in data-sharing contracts. These contracts ensure that:

- The data provider is obligated to share high-quality data.

³² IEPD, Risk Management and Impact Assessment on the Processing of Personal Data, 2021, p. 17.

- The data recipient is responsible for implementing appropriate security measures to protect the data.

Moreover, SYNTHIA will use the Federated Learning Platform, allowing the remote training of AI models and the remote use of models for SDG without the need to share the data. The datasets will not be transferred from the hospital and clinical nodes (Federated Nodes), significantly reducing the risk of unauthorized access, modification, or deletion of the data. As specified in D1.2 DMP, SYNTHIA infrastructure leverages existing FAIR-aligned resources. Moreover, the use of Secure Multi-Party Computation (SMPC) and Differential Privacy (DP) will maintain the privacy of special category data while allowing federated learning processes to interact seamlessly across distributed nodes.

After the beginning of the project, some partners indicated that certain datasets cannot be processed via the Federated Infrastructure due to limitations imposed by national regulations. In situations where the federated learning approach cannot be implemented, alternative solutions for providing access to the datasets in question will be explored, ensuring compliance with national data access legislation and data protection regulations. More detailed information will be included in further versions of the DMP (which is intended to be a living document and will contain updates and further details about the data flows, and other data management aspects within the project) .

Additionally, data providers must comply with additional data security requirements established on the national level. For example, HUS specifies that it can share even anonymous data only after the Finnish Social and Health Data Permit Authority (Findata) authorizes the export of anonymous data.

In addition, WP7 will evaluate and clinically validate the SD to ensure its quality and privacy.

What is the level of residual risk?

Acceptable.

Risk 2. Algorithmic Bias and Discrimination

What are the main risk sources and threats that could lead to this risk?

The main source of this risk arises from the training and validation of AI used for generating SD, which largely depends on the quality of the data used. For example, if the data is biased, the AI trained on it may not only reproduce those biases but potentially amplify them. If the training data lacks the necessary quality and this issue is not addressed during AI model development, such as by identifying the appropriate SDG tool, the AI may produce biased outputs. These biases could then lead to discriminatory decisions affecting certain individuals or groups.

What could be the main impact on the data subjects?

If the selected synthetic data generation approach does not account for this risk, the produced SD could reinforce existing biases in the raw data or even exacerbate them.

How do you estimate the risk severity?

Severe, given that SYNTHIA aims to maximize the potential of SDG in healthcare by developing and validating reliable tools for specific medical applications.

How do you estimate the likelihood of the risk?

Remote. The likelihood of the risk of developing a discriminatory SDG producing biased synthetic data without adopting mitigating measures is high; however, it is the further use of the biased data for further training and implementation of AI-powered recommender systems, for instance in practice, which might give biased decisions and therefore be discriminatory and violate patients' rights. The use of the generated data is not the purpose of the Project. In any case, the Project will implement mitigating measures to not produce discriminatory output.

What mitigating measures will address this risk?

WP6 is dedicated to SDG and aims to ensure that AI training remains unbiased.

On the one hand, there is currently not enough information available to accurately assess the quality of the data collected and processed for AI training and validation. On the other hand, the project is structured to mitigate this risk through dedicated work packages (WPs) aimed at ensuring high-quality data collection and processing. Specifically:

- WP3 outlines the data required for each use case.
- WP4 ensures the availability of high-quality, harmonized data for SDG researchers. For instance, CERTH will contribute to data harmonization and quality assurance.
- WP6 conducts an extensive review of the state of the art in SDG, helping to explore, develop, and integrate SDG tools into the SYNTHIA infrastructure. For instance, CERTH contributing to SDG and applying statistical balancing approaches to reduce the underrepresentation of certain patient groups.
- WP7 evaluates synthetic data, identifying its advantages and limitations for clinical applications. The conditions under which WP7 conducts these evaluations will be explored with the support of UNIVIE, aiming to ensure compliance with the GDPR.
- WP8 provides support in identifying and addressing ethical, legal, and societal issues relevant to the project, including those concerning AI, in particular drafting of the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) (D8.4) due in M42.

Additionally, UNIVIE will help address potential bias by contributing to ethical, legal, and societal aspects of SYNTHIA's study protocols. This includes:

- Researching and drafting the current legal, privacy, and ethical framework for using SD in healthcare (T8.2).
- Exploring and addressing the implications of SD use in healthcare and citizens' concerns regarding its adoption (T8.3 and T8.4).

These efforts ensure that SYNTHIA remains aligned with ethical and regulatory standards while mitigating bias in AI applications.

What is the level of residual risk?

Acceptable.

Risk 3: Patient withdrawing consent

What are the main risk sources and threats that could lead to this risk?

The main risk source would be human error in missing or overlooking withdrawal of consent requests or absence or ineffective cooperation at the level of the Project. The data controller providing the data might fail to inform other joint controllers about the withdrawal of consent, and/or the joint controllers might fail to remove the data from processing activities in SYNTHIA.

What could be the main impact on the data subjects?

This risk might lead to unlawful processing of the data, infringing EU and national data protection law, in particular, breach of the principle of data processing on the basis of informed consent based on Article 6(1)(a) in conjunction with Article 9(2)(a) GDPR, collected by clinical partners.

How do you estimate the risk severity?

Severe, given unauthorized processing of special category data is an unlawful practice.

How do you estimate the likelihood of the risk?

Remote. Patients can withdraw their consent, but there is no data showing that patients do this often enough to significantly increase the likelihood of this risk materializing. Nonetheless, mitigating measures should be implemented at the Consortium level to ensure an appropriate balance between the legitimate interests of the Consortium in conducting research and the rights of data subjects

What mitigating measures will address this risk?

Although patients may withdraw consent, the relevant data provider can implement the data subject's request independently, without needing to inform other partners or wait for their response. This is possible because SYNTHIA processes data within a federated environment without sharing personal data. This setup enables data providers to handle data subject requests efficiently, avoiding delays caused by inter-partner coordination.

Moreover, if pseudonymized data is shared, a data-sharing contract will outline the obligations of all parties, including the duty to cooperate in handling data subject requests. These controls ensure that the data subject's requests for consent withdrawal and data deletion are satisfied—unless an alternative legal basis for data processing remains applicable.

What is the level of residual risk?

Acceptable.

Risk 4: Lack of transparency in data processing

What are the main risk sources and threats that could lead to this risk?

The requirement of transparency is about being clear, open, and honest with people from the start about who you are and how and why you use their personal data. If data subjects do not know that their data is being processed or are unaware or were provided with insufficient information about the purposes of the processing, this might lead to their mistrust and prejudice to the Project and its outcomes, in particular in relation to SDG and SD.

What could be the main impact on the data subjects?

The main impact on data subjects could be the inability to fully exercise their rights under the GDPR, such as the right to transparent information, access, rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, data portability, and the right to object. Furthermore, the data subjects might develop a negative perception of SD, which could affect their decision-making in areas related to SD, potentially leading to adverse long-term effects on their health.

How do you estimate the risk severity?

This risk might have a severe impact on data subject rights, as it involves special category data and might undermine public trust in the Project.

How do you estimate the likelihood of the risk?

Remote. Data controllers are already subject to national and European data protection laws, including the obligation to provide patients with the information required under the GDPR and other relevant regulations. However, mitigating measures at the Consortium level remain necessary to ensure that data processing for the purposes of the Project is transparent to patients.

What mitigating measures will address this risk?

SYNTHIA partners adhere to the requirements of European and national data protection laws, with support from UNIVIE on ethical and legal matters. The data minimization principle is upheld in that data users in the Project do not require and do not expect to receive personal data for processing. This data will be processed in the federated environment. Moreover, the information about the project is published on the dedicated website: <https://www.ih-synthia.eu/>. The contact point for data subjects should be agreed upon by the Beneficiaries and clearly communicated to the data subjects. Furthermore, the responsibility to inform data subjects about the processing of their personal data within the Project lies with the respective data controllers, in accordance with their obligations under the GDPR.

What is the level of residual risk?

Acceptable.

Risk 5: Re-identification of data subjects

What are the main risk sources and threats that could lead to this risk?

A number of partners mentioned that pseudonymized personal data might be shared within the Project. This raises the issue of the reidentification of data subjects.

What could be the main impact on the data subjects?

Reidentification of a data subject might lead to a violation of the right to the protection of personal data, which might cause various negative consequences to data subjects.

How do you estimate the risk severity?

Severe, as data processed in the Project is health data, which by nature is a special category of data.

How do you estimate the likelihood of the risk?

Remote. Due to ongoing technological progress, the risk of re-identification may increase over time and therefore requires regular re-evaluation. The Consortium is committed to minimizing the sharing of pseudonymised data and limits it to cases where no alternative exists, in these situations the necessary mitigating measures to manage this risk effectively will be adopted.

What mitigating measures will address this risk?

As has been already noted above, all partners are obliged to abide by data protection regulations. A number of partners informed us about specific security measures aimed at ensuring that the risk of reidentification will not materialize. Such partners as GEHC reported about internal procedures to ensure that the data transferred to them contains no personal identifiers or any kind of privacy breach.

Moreover, SYNTHIA will employ a federated learning platform for processing the data, which significantly reduces any risk of reidentification (see above). If no viable alternatives are available, pseudonymised data may be shared, subject to appropriate data processing or data sharing agreements negotiated and signed with the support of UNIVIE.

What is the level of residual risk?

Acceptable.

Conclusions, Next Steps and Recommendations

This DPIA represents the first iteration and may be updated as needed, particularly if changes in processing operations alter the associated risks. In this initial assessment, planned activities have been outlined, and five key risks to data subjects' rights have been identified. All these risks are considered low-level due to their remote likelihood and the implementation of mitigating measures.

Key mitigating measures include:

- Processing data within a federated environment,
- Sharing pseudonymized data only when necessary, and
- Ensuring that any data sharing occurs under contractual obligations aligned with the GDPR.

Next Steps for the Consortium to Ensure GDPR Compliance:

1. Validation and review of DPIA report by DPOs and/or privacy experts.
2. Negotiation and signing of necessary agreements, such as data-sharing agreements.
3. Governance framework development (D8.2), led by WP8, due M24.
4. Assessment using the ALTAI framework (D8.4), conducted by WP8, due M42.
5. Ongoing monitoring by WP8 of data processing in SYNTHIA, including changes in context and the introduction of new external factors, to assess their impact on the risk assessment in this DPIA.

Recommendations for consortium partners:

Each consortium partner is advised to:

1. Define a mechanism for exercising data subject rights (designate which entities are responsible).
2. To ensure legal compliance with GDPR, several partners that indicate that their software solutions are yet to be determined must kindly provide the relevant details in a timely manner before the finalization of this DPIA report.
3. Assess the partner's role under the GDPR (e.g., data controller, data processor, or joint controller) in consultation with its Data Protection Officer (DPO) or legal team or privacy team, if applicable.
4. Evaluate whether the partner's processing activities meet the conditions of Article 35(1) GDPR and, if so, conduct and implement an internal DPIA, taking into account risks identified in the present (Consortium-level) DPIA.
5. Refer to WP8 for guidance on legal, ethical, or societal issues, including the interpretation and application of the GDPR, AI Act, or other relevant European regulations.

Annex 1 – DPIA Questionnaire

Annex 2 – DPIA Participants

Section A: General information

A1. Please, provide your full name and contact e-mail.

name

surname

e-mail

designation (your role e.g., Data Protection Officer, lawyer, scientist, etc)

A2. Which SYNTHIA partner do you represent?

IISLAFE

BSC

LUMC

UNIBO

IRCCS-S

IRCCS-A

PATVO

MAT

CHA

HUS

ICH

TRAIN

UPM

CERTH

EMBL

ITTM

i-HD

ERASMUS

FRAUNHOFER

VHIO

VHIR

EAPM

- DNV
- PFIZER
- GEHC
- GEHC-DE
- GEHC-HU
- GEHC-ES
- JANSSEN
- GV
- NOVO
- BMS
- CHUV
- NICE
- Pfizer Pharma
- GEHC UK
- GEHC IN
- GEHC US

A3. Are you a Data Provider, Recipient, both or something else? Please select all that may apply.

Data provider

Comment

Data recipient

Comment

Please explain, if something else

Comment

A4. Provide contact details of your data protection officer (DPO).

name

surname

E-mail

designation

A5. Provide contact details of your legal team.

name

surname

E-mail

A6. Provide contact details of your Research and Development Department.

name

surname

E-mail

designation

Section B: Data processing

B1. Which Work Packages (WPs) and parts of the project are you working on? Please select all that may apply.

Please describe briefly what you will be precisely doing, and include the relevant use case or task number.

WP1

Comment

WP2

Comment

WP3

Comment

WP4

Comment

WP5

Comment

WP6

Comment

WP7

Comment

WP8

Comment

WP9

Comment

WP10

Comment

B2. What data do you intend to share /need to receive /need to capture?

Provide a list of data, e.g. clinical data, patients records, multimodality data, treatment data etc.

B3. What formats are you expecting to share with /receive using?

Provide a list of data formats. e.g. OMOP, DICOM, Tabular etc.

B4. For what purposes do you intend to share the data and/or expect to receive data?

Please select all that may apply.

Provide a list of potential users.

Synthetic data (SD) generation. Please specify use case(s).

Comment

SD evaluation, quality assurance and clinical validation

Comment

If other, please specify

Comment

B5. Do you intend to anonymise or pseudonymise the data?

If yes, please specify the de-identification methods and processes you will apply. Additionally, indicate whether the final result will be anonymised or pseudonymised data.

Pseudonymisation is not the same as anonymisation. The GDPR defines pseudonymisation as processing personal data so it cannot be linked to a specific individual without additional, separately kept information protected by safeguards. Since such data can still identify individuals, it remains personal data. In contrast, anonymous data cannot be linked to individuals at all and falls outside the GDPR's scope.

Section C: Data security

C1. What is the name of the infrastructure solution you will be using for SYNTHIA?

Please include details of the infrastructure and any service you use to provide it.

C2. Describe the architecture of your infrastructure solution used for SYNTHIA.

Please include details around whether it is Cloud based, Dockerised, dedicated virtual or physical servers?

C3. What software (and/or Third-Party Applications) will you run on the infrastructure for management and service provision?

Please also include details for software used for Operating Systems, incident management and resource allocation.

C4. Do you have security software installed?

Please provide details of any antivirus, managed firewall and security incident response systems in place.

C5. Do you routinely update your service software?

Please provide any relevant information including operating system updated and security patches.

C6. Where are your services run from? Are they outside the EEA?

This covers all your services and software (including Third-Party Applications).

C7. Do you consider any other technical or physical risks to data quality, data integrity, or data security, e.g. AI-specific risks?

If yes, please specify, also detailing any relevant measures taken/to be taken to mitigate against/prevent such risks from arising.

Section D: Data subjects rights

D1. Please identify the legal basis for your processing of personal data (Art. 6 GDPR and/or Art.9 GDPR). If more than one, please specify all legal bases.

If you are referring to national legislation, please provide the name of the law and the relevant article.

D2. Do you intend to notify data subjects that their data will be processed in SYNTHIA and inform them of their rights under the GDPR?

If yes, please specify the procedure. If no, please explain the reason, e.g., you are not the data provider and believe the data provider should notify the data subjects.

D3. Consider the impact your processing might have on data subjects' rights and identify if your processing causes any of the following risks. Please specify the likelihood and severity of the possible harm.

Likelihood of harm: remote or reasonable possibility.

Severity of impact: some impact or serious harm.

inability to exercise rights (including but not limited to privacy rights)

Comment

inability to access services or opportunities

Comment

loss of control over the use of personal data

Comment

discrimination

Comment

identity theft or fraud

Comment

financial loss

Comment

reputational damage

Comment

physical harm

Comment

loss of confidentiality

Comment

re-identification of pseudonymised data or anonymised data

Comment

any other significant economic or social disadvantage

Comment

emotional /psychological distress

Comment

D4. Specify the mitigating measures to address the identified risks, e.g., use of federated environments, pseudonymisation of data, etc

D5. List any other relevant organizational, security, or technical measures that you have in place (or are planning to take) to ensure data protection.

D6. Do you intend to share personal data (or its results) outside of the EU? (e.g. to any entity operating outside the EU, or any entity within the EU that has its main establishment outside of the EU? If yes, please specify and provide details.

D7. Please add below any other information you think is relevant.

Thank you for your time.

You can edit your answers any time using the same link.

	SYNTHIA partner	Completion Status
1	IISLAFE	Yes
1	IISLAFE	Yes
2	BSC	Yes
3	LUMC	Yes
4	UNIBO	Yes
4.1	IRCCS-S	Yes
4.2	IRCCS-A	Yes
5	PATVO	not required
6	MAT	not required
7	CHA	Yes
8	HUS	Yes
8	HUS	Yes
9	ICH	No
10	TRAIN	No
11	UPM	Yes
12	CERTH	Yes
13	EMBL	Yes
14	ITTM	Yes
15	i-HD	Yes
16	ERASMUS	Yes
18	FRAUNHOFER	Yes
19	VHIO	Yes
20	VHIR	Yes
21	EAPM	not required
22	DNV	Yes
23	PFIZER	Yes
24	GEHC	Yes
25	JANSSEN	No
26	GV	Yes
27	NOVO	No
28	BMS	Yes
29	CHUV	No
30	NICE	Yes
30	NICE	Yes
31	Pfizer Pharma	Yes (Pfizer)